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Acronyms and abbreviations

AMEG	Africa Makerspace Ecosystem Gathering
AMN	Africa Makerspace Network
AOSH	Africa Open Science Hardware
API	application programming interface
APSOHA	Association pour la Promotion de la Science Ouverte en Haïti et en Afrique
B2B	business-to-business
CLI	Collective Leadership Institute
DI	Digital Innovation
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DM	distributed manufacturing
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	digital object identifier
DoW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
F2F	founder-to-founder
FGD	focus group discussion
GA	Grant Agreement
GDIW	Ghana Digital Innovation Week

GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (EU)
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering
GreenTec	GreenTec Capital Africa Foundation
H2020	Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union
IAAC	Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia
IMA	Innovative Manufacturing in Africa
IOP Alliance	Internet of Production Alliance
IPRs	intellectual property rights
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	key performance indicator
MiR	Makers-in-Residency
MOOC	massive open online course
NGO	non-governmental organisation
OCBM	Open Catalogue of Business Models
OERs	open educational resources
OMT	Open Makerspace Toolkit
Open AIR	Open African Innovation Research network
PSS	People and Skills Specification
PU	public
REFFAO	ReFFAO –Réseau Francophone des FabLab d’Afrique de l’Ouest

RISA	Research and Innovation Systems for Africa
STEM	science, technology, engineering and mathematics
ToT	training-of-trainers
UCT	University of Cape Town
UNHCR	UN Refugee Agency
WP	work package
Y1	project year one
Y2	project year two
Y3	project year three
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation

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Executive summary

The **African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem (mAKE) project**, funded under the EU Horizon 2020 programme, ran from 2022 to 2025 and focused on fostering innovation, sustainability, and socio-economic growth through makerspaces and other hardware-focused Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in Africa and Europe. In three years, the initiative made significant strides in supporting entrepreneurship, capacity building, and sustainable practices in makerspaces/DIHs while establishing makerspaces as vital components of local and global innovation ecosystems.

The project provided critical support to startups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) linked to makerspaces/DIHs. Through tailored interventions, the venture building programme delivered over 130 hours of personalised support for 20 startups to enhance their business models, financial strategies, prospecting, and marketing activities. This effort was further bolstered by the Venture Building Handbook, a comprehensive guide available in English and French, which became a key resource for entrepreneurs and makerspace managers, facilitating the transformation of ideas into scalable, sustainable businesses.

Another important achievement of the project was the Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM), co-created with input from over 350 stakeholders. This living document provides makerspaces with adaptable business model elements to achieve financial sustainability. It has already been successfully adopted by more than 10 makerspaces, demonstrating its utility in diverse contexts and settings. Additionally, the Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme facilitated knowledge-sharing and cross-cultural collaboration and amongst African and European makers. The programme connected four African innovators with European makerspaces, fostering collaborative innovation, co-creation, and peer-to-peer skills development.

The mAKE project also prioritised policy advocacy, engaging 69 stakeholders from Africa and Europe to co-develop a Common Policy Agenda. The agenda was disseminated to policy makers and the maker ecosystem via 10 meetings with policy makers at local, national, and international levels. This initiative contributed to raising the recognition, in political fora, of makerspaces as critical infrastructure, and demonstrated their potential to drive local manufacturing, capacity building, and economic development.

Another core project output is the Open Makerspace Toolkit (OMT), which provides high-quality content guidance for makerspace representatives on how to set up and sustain an inclusive makerspace, and how to manage interactions with, communicate efficiently with, the various stakeholders who interact with makerspaces. The OMT training-of-trainers (ToT) programme has ensured that the Toolkit is disseminated widely and effectively. Approximately 70 trainers participated in the OMT ToT programme, creating a strong network of skilled makerspace trainers capable of cascading their knowledge to others.

The mAKE massive open online course (MOOC) is an important instrument to sustain the most important achievements of the mAKE project. The MOOC provides project-developed resources such as the OCBM, the Venture Building Handbook, and the Common Policy Agenda, along with additional training materials, to the makerspace ecosystem. Thus, the MOOC enables a broad audience to engage with the project's frameworks and tools, fostering a global culture of shared learning and innovation. Already, since the MOOC's official launch in January 2025, 68 people have registered on the mAKE MOOC platform.

The project's distributed manufacturing (DM) innovations included a Maker Passport system prototype, where 45 makers signed up in order to test a possible certification (and thus mutual recognition) of their skills to allow for integration into distributed production ecosystems. Also supporting DM is the project's Map of Machinery, which has to date catalogued more than 10,300 manufacturing resources. In addition, a digital contracting system for DM was trialed by approximately 90 people during the runtime of the project, thus raising awareness of the potential of DM and fostering important dialogue on drivers and motivators of local manufacturing.

The mAKE project also explored innovative financing mechanisms, enabling makerspaces to tap into diverse funding streams such as crowdfunding, corporate sponsorships, and community-backed financial models. By addressing traditional funding gaps, these approaches enhanced the financial resilience of makerspaces and encouraged sustainable growth. Over its three years, the project engaged over 500 businesses and stakeholders through workshops, matchmaking events, and capacity-building initiatives.

Policymakers also showed keen interest, with 42 officials attending events to engage with the project's outputs. These efforts resulted in enduring partnerships, including the strengthening of the Global Innovation Gathering and the newly inaugurated African Makerspace Ecosystem, which will continue to amplify the project's impact.

Despite challenges, including visa restrictions for African participants that hindered international collaboration, the project demonstrated the power of community-driven solutions and tailored interventions. It revealed critical gaps in financial literacy, entrepreneurship support, and policy integration, which were addressed through targeted programmes and resources. The integration of community voices throughout the project ensured that mAKE's tools and frameworks are highly relevant, and at the same time adaptable to diverse cultural and operational contexts.

The mAKE project leaves a legacy as a catalyst for sustainable innovation and socioeconomic development. By fostering grassroots creativity, building global partnerships, and promoting policy alignment, the project has laid a robust foundation for continued growth and impact. The tools, resources, and networks established through this initiative stand as a model for empowering makerspaces/DIHs worldwide, driving inclusive innovation and resilience in local and global economies.

To ensure the long-term impact of the mAKE project, it is recommended that policy makers and stakeholders institutionalise its outputs by embedding them into local and regional innovation strategies. Governments should recognise and support makerspaces as essential components of innovation ecosystems, integrating them into education, economic development, and sustainability agendas. Additionally, ongoing funding mechanisms, including public-private partnerships and international grants, should be cultivated to provide financial stability for makerspaces. Finally, establishing monitoring and evaluation frameworks will help track the effectiveness of these initiatives, allowing for the continued refinement of resources and their alignment to evolving community needs. Through these efforts, the transformative impact of the mAKE project can be amplified, ensuring that its legacy endures and continues to benefit communities worldwide.

This document, titled Final Impact Assessment Report, has been developed within the framework of the mAKE project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No. 101016858.

1. Introduction

The evaluation and impact assessment of the mAkE project, which constituted mAkE work package 7 (WP7), had two main objectives. First, we wanted to ensure that the project's network structures, capacity building support, created infrastructures, and materials were developed according to the project plan and were contributing to the project objectives. Second, we aimed to provide evidence of the envisioned impact, and to identify facts and stories that demonstrated the project's influence beyond the borders of the consortium, particularly in terms of capacity building.

WP7 published an Interim Evaluation Report (D7.2) in January 2024, which provided an overview of (i) the main project outputs, initial outcomes, and important lessons learnt across WPs 1 to 6 up to the end of Y2 (end-January 2024); and (ii) the potential future sources of impact assessment data in in project year three (Y3) from February 2024 to January 2025.

This final report takes a look at the project outputs, outcomes and important lessons learnt across the entire three-year project period. It shows that mAkE has generated a broad range of outputs in strong collaboration with, and via co-creation with, its diverse stakeholders—ranging from guidelines and handbooks to policy briefs, training materials and supporting infrastructures. To create these outputs, sustainable engagement with the makerspace ecosystem was established, eliciting the needs of the different stakeholders involved, including makers, makerspace managers, enterprise founders, investors, policy makers, and educators. This involvement allowed the mAkE consortium members, when iteratively developing and shaping the mAkE resources, to understand, consider, and address the great diversity of contexts, needs and motivations present in African and European makerspace/DIH ecosystems.

This document is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1: Introduction**
- **Chapter 2: General project KPIs**
- **Chapters 3–8: WP1–WP6**

Each of these six chapters presents the outputs (KPIs) and outcomes for a WP; feedback from the involved stakeholders in the form of “community voices”; and the main lessons learned .

- **Chapter 9: Summary & Conclusions: Overall KPIs and lessons learned at the end of year 3**
Provides a summary of the project KPIs and outcomes at the end of year 3.
- **Additional references**

2. General project KPIs

The table below provides a general overview of project WPs' key performance indicators (KPIs) and KPI targets initially defined in our project plan, and the status of reaching them at the end of the project (end of Y3). KPIs were only one part of the project evaluation and impact assessment processes. The qualitative outcomes, impact stories, and important lessons learnt generated in this project are set out in Chapters 3–8 of this report.

Table 1: General Project KPIs

WP	KPIs	KPI targets	KPIs reached at the end of Y3
WP1	Supported companies (green startups or SMEs) in venture building	20	20 companies supported
WP1	Supported makerspaces in venture building	10	21 makerspace experts supported (through ToT) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 14 received ToT certificate - 7 joined fewer than 60% of the workshop sessions and did not qualify for certificate
WP1	Company building support services	100 hours	131 hours
All WPs	Engaged businesses (makerspaces, founders, early-stage investors, corporates, NGOs, etc.) in mAKE activities	500	<p>WP1: approx. 413 businesses engaged</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - estimation without duplicates based on the venture building events, including ToT, MiR, Matchmaking events, interviews for Funding Mechanisms Report + approx. 79 for the OCBM. <p>WP4: approx. 243 businesses engaged</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - interviews, surveys, working groups sessions, workshops.
WP1	Business models applied	10	10 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 makerspaces went through first Makerspace Mentoring Programme (MMP)

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 7 makerspaces in second MMP run under year 2 of Innovative Manufacturing in Africa (IMA) project (companion project to mAKE)
WP1	Co-created digital innovations with ecological impact in the mAKE hubs' networks	10	5 during the MiR programme
WP2	Requests for and access to the Common Policy Agenda (e.g., downloads)	50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 368 downloads of the Policy Agenda on the mAKE website between the months of October 20th, 2024 to January 30th, 2025.¹ - 78 downloads of the 2-pager Policy brief on the mAKE website in the same period. - Approximately 100 printed copies of the Policy Agenda shared at events including: co-design session with Distributed Design Platform in Barcelona (Feb. 2024), Afrilabs Cape Town (Nov. 2024) and Africa Makerspace Ecosystem Gathering (AMEG) Cape Town (Nov. 2024)
WP2	Meetings with policy makers at local, national and international levels	4	<p>Approx: 10</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-design meeting with Distributed Design Platform (Barcelona, Feb. 2024) - Transformation Literacy Conference organized by the Collective Leadership Institute (CLI), (online, Apr. 2024) - Ghana Hubs Network conference (Takoradi, Apr. 2024) - Africa Open Science Hardware Summit (Accra, Jul. 2024) - Wind Empowerment Conference, Greece (Ioannina, Oct. 2024) - Re:publica (Berlin, May 2024) - Afrilabs (Cape Town, Nov. 2024) - Africa Makerspace Ecosystem Gathering (AMEG), (Cape Town, Nov. 2024) - Vulca Seminar (Erlangen, Germany, Nov2024)

¹ Due to technical problems of the access statistics tool, only data from November 2024 onwards were saved.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community call (online, Dec. 2023) - Fab City Summit (Yucatan, Aug. 2024)
WP2	Policy makers attending our meetings	20	<p>Approx: 42</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Approx. 2 at a co-design meeting with Distributed Design Platform (incl. educators and representatives of policy design organisations from around Europe). - Approx. 7 at Ghana Hubs Network conference (incl. Director of Communication from the National Entrepreneurship and Innovation Programme (NEIP), a GIZ representative, the Dean of Languages at Takoradi Technical University (TTU), representatives from the Ghana Association of Industry, Ghana National Chamber of Commerce, Ghana National Youth Employment Agency). - Approx. 4 at the CLI Transformation Literacy Conference (incl. representatives from the CLI, Namibia’s International University of Management, and Madagascar’s Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development) - Approx. 2 at the Africa Open Science Hardware Summit (incl. representative from the Ministry of Environment, Science and Technology Ghana, educators, and researchers) - Approx. 3 at Wind Empowerment Conference (incl. Professor from University of Zurich, educators from France, representatives of policy transformation organisations in renewable energy, and engineers). - Approx. 2 at Re:publica (incl. German Minister, researchers) - Approx. 15 at Afrilabs (incl. South African Minister of Small Business, advisors to Ministers from Africa, policy advocacy groups in South Africa, Uganda, Sierra Leone and Ghana, makers from both Africa and Europe, foundations, educators and researchers).

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Approx. 5 at AMEG (incl. representatives of foundations, educators from South African universities, government representatives, researchers). - Approx. 2 at the Vulca Seminar (incl. makers, engineers, advisors to governments, entrepreneurs). - Approx. 2 at the Fab City Summit (incl. makers, engineers, government officials researchers)
WP3	Open educational resources (OERs) collected in the mAKE library	100	<p>125 in total</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 81 in English - 44 in French
WP3	People accessing the learning resources (from year 3 on)	1500	<p>This number looks into the future, but we see that the main learning resources created by mAKE have been accessed as follows:</p> <p>Downloads from the mAKE website between Oct 20th, 2024 and Jan 30th, 2025:</p> <p>Open Catalogue of Business Models: 309 times</p> <p>Venture Building Handbook (English): 330 times</p> <p>Venture Building Handbook (French): 97 times</p> <p>Makerspace Toolkit: 185 times</p> <p>Registration to the MOOC in Jan 2025: 68</p>
WP3	People accessing the Open Makerspace Toolkit (OMT) (digital version)	500	<p>From Nov 2023 to Jan 2025, we received 1312 visitors in total.</p> <p>The document was downloaded 185 times from the mAKE website, only between Oct 20th, 2024, to Jan, 30th 2025.</p>
WP3	People per year accessing the mAKE MOOC online	100 (in Y3)	<p>In January 2025, the MOOC launch webinars were attended by:</p>

	platform		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 73 attendees (English webinar) - 22 attendees (French webinar) <p>As of end-January 2025 (end of Y3), 68 people were registered on the mAKE MOOC platform.</p>
All WPs	Training and capacity building events (20 attendees each)	80 events	<p>WP1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 Skill-Building Matchmaking events - 1 ToT workshop building on the Venture Building Handbook - 8 webinars organised for training on Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM) elements <p>WP2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 webinar on the Common Policy Agenda <p>WP3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 ToT building on Open Makerspace Toolkit (OMT) - 1 webinar (in English) on use of the MOOC <p>WP4:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 workshop on building the Maker Passport system - 1 Distributed Contracting workshop (at AMEG 2024 in Cape Town)
All WPs	Training and capacity building events (10-20 attendees each)		<p>WP1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 pitch trainings - 2 ToT workshops - 4 Skill-Building Matchmaking events - 1 Impact/Hybrid Fund workshop (in Jan. 25) - 1 Distributed Contracting workshop - 3 introductions to OCBM <p>WP3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 4 ToT workshops building on Open

			<p>Makerspace Toolkit</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 webinar (in French) on use of the MOOC
All WPs	Training and capacity building events (3-10 attendees each)		<p>WP1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 Skill-Building Matchmaking Events <p>WP4:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 project planning workshop for MiR - 1 workshop on Exchange of Manufacturing Data - 15 Skills Working Group sessions - 18 Map of Machinery Working Group sessions - 7 Distributed Contracting Workshops
WP4	References to open standards	500	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 629 views on a single post on People and Skills Specification (PSS) open standard, on the IOP Community Forum (44 posts mentioning the PSS and 14 mentioning the Maker Passport). - 268 views of deliverable 4.1 on the PSS open standard, and 144 on the PSS standard's page on PubPub.
WP4	Open standards adopted	50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 167 downloads of mAKE deliverable 4.1 on the PSS open standard, which showed in using the standard via a Maker Passport system.
WP4	Entries in the Map of Machinery	500	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - overall count of 20,000 records, and 10,308 unique records after filtering out
WP4	People testing the Digital Contracting System	150	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contracting for distributed manufacturing (DM) was tested by 27 makers with a model contract in 2023. Since October 2024, another approx. 62 people have tested the digital contracting system based on the learning of previous research and the DM trials.

WP4	people using the open standard for maker skills (Maker Passport)	150	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- 45 people have signed up for Maker Passports through the IMA project.- Continued work with REFFAO on development and testing of community-based authentication for Maker Passport is planned (REFFAO network counts over 20 FabLabs in 7 countries, and over 30,000 members)
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3. Venture building and business models (WP1)

This work package (WP1) collected, analysed, and provided information on the objectives and operating models of successful makerspaces/DIHs. It provided targeted matchmaking opportunities between digital innovators, SMEs, businesses, investors, public bodies, academic institutions and NGOs in Europe and Africa, and aimed to identify potential investors to catalyse more private capital for investment in digital social innovation. The WP1 achievements are presented below in terms of four core outcomes: 3.1 Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM), 3.2. Venture Building and Business Development programme, 3.3 Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme and matchmaking activities; and 3.4 Innovative Funding Mechanisms.

3.1 Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM)

Outputs:

The Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM) is a living document that provides 17 modular business model elements for makerspaces and DIHs. It aims to help makerspaces and DIHs in adapting their business strategies and aligning them to their unique objectives, cultural contexts, and community needs. It was published on the mAKE website as downloadable PDF document and as living website under: <https://localeconomies.org>², which allows for a more natural navigation between models than the pdf version, and additional information and functionality can be added as needed.

The OCBM was co-designed with a strong engagement of the makerspace ecosystem, including all members of the MAKE consortium, and members of the communities represented in the consortium, including GiG, AfricaOSH, AMN, and the Fab City network. Six in-person co-creation workshops were held with around 100 people (in Germany, Indonesia, Cameroon, and South Africa). Eight webinars with more than 200 participants were organized to collect input on specific business models or business model elements, such as consultancy, manufacturing networks, and working with artisans. In addition, 50 individual interviews with successful DIHs/makerspaces were conducted representing a cross-section of sectors, geographic foci, and scale. These interviews were the main sources of content and framing for the catalogue, supplemented by the co-creation workshops and online community discussions.

Three makerspaces from Africa and Europe were invited to a OCBM mentoring program. The mentoring programme generated case studies of implementation of the business model catalogue in three different

² The Internet of Production Alliance (IOP), received funding, under the UK International Development-funded [Research and Innovation Systems for Africa \(RISA\) Fund](#), for a programme including creating a website version of the OCBM.

local contexts and helped us to investigate the applicability and usefulness of the OCBM. The programme started in November 2023 and was running for six months with Habitat Augsburg in Germany, Garoua in Cameroon, and iZone Hub in Zimbabwe.

Another 7 makerspaces in Africa have been through a mentoring program funded by RISA (see footnote above) to make use of the OCBM. The OCBM was also one of the resources, which got high attention during the final mAkE dissemination events in 2024. The access statistics show that **309 people downloaded it from the mAkE website (only between Oct 20, 2024 and January, 2025) and 133 unique visitors accessed the website localeconomies.org** with numbers increasing steadily every month.

Outcomes:

Through the close collaboration during the creation and mentoring of the OCBM it became evident that makerspace experts tend to focus heavily on creating social impact, often prioritizing social and community-driven goals over entrepreneurial considerations. While this aligns well with their backgrounds, it also reveals a gap in their understanding of running a business sustainably. The OCBM very successfully addressed this gap.

Based on interviews/participant feedback, the mentees highly appreciated the adaptable and flexible format of the OCBM that allowed them to explore new business model ideas that fit their specific objectives and context. The OCBM provided the involved makerspaces with concrete ideas and case studies on how existing businesses could run more sustainably. Thus, it not only raised awareness and knowledge on different business models for makerspaces and DIHs, but some of them have already been successfully implemented by the makerspaces at the end of the mAkE project, as the following “community voices” (see image below) show.

A table that provides a summary of main outputs and outcomes related to the OCBM can be found in [Annex 1](#).

Community Voices: mentees feedback on the OCBM

Building Financially Sustainable Makerspaces Through the Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM)

As makerspaces continue to inspire innovation and empower communities, financial sustainability remains a key challenge. The **Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM)**, developed through collaborative input from global makerspaces, offers a flexible solution. This "living document" is designed to help makerspaces adapt business strategies that align with their unique objectives, cultural contexts, and community needs. By providing modular business model elements, the OCBM enables makerspaces to craft tailored paths toward sustainability.

The Concept Behind OCBM: A Toolkit, Not a Template

Makerspaces thrive when sharing stories of innovation, learning, and community impact; however, discussions on financial sustainability are typically more reserved.

"We saw the need for something like a buffet — that people running makerspaces can browse through to gain ideas, choosing elements that seem relevant to what they are trying to create. This is the idea behind the OCBM."
 ---Anna Sera Lowe, Manufacturing Change Ltd, creator of the OCBM---

Co-Creating the OCBM: Input from a Global Community

The OCBM was co-developed with input from 50 representatives from makerspaces and distributed manufacturing organisations across Africa and Europe, ensuring it reflected a wide spectrum of business models and entrepreneurial insights. The inputs were compiled with the assistance of **Martin Oloo**, CEO of Fablab Winam, and **Gertrude Mawuena Goh**, researcher into the marketing practices of makerspaces.

A Path Forward: Expanding OCBM's Reach

There is strong interest in expanding the programme to include more makerspaces, particularly across Africa. Available at LocalEconomies.org the OCBM is continuously updated, incorporating new insights and case studies to support a diverse array of makerspaces worldwide.

Early Success Stories: OCBM in Action

In 2023, a mentoring programme was launched, inviting makerspaces to explore how to apply elements of the OCBM to achieve financial independence.

Ronald from iZone Hub in Zimbabwe

shared that the mentoring programme was instrumental in his makerspace's journey towards sustainability.

"It was great how flexible the Open Business Model Catalogue was. We could adapt it to the needs of our makerspace. It was not made in stone, but an encouragement and provided new ideas to make small changes that fit in the current systems."

With guidance from mentors, the team explored alternative revenue streams, such as partnering with organisations to fund training initiatives and offering 3D printing services.

"In one of our sprints, we realised with the support of our mentor that we can try to partner with other organisations to come in and pay for the training. It opened our eyes."

Eric from Garoua Makerspace in Cameroon

highlighted the value of exchanging experiences with other makerspaces and learning from diverse mentors.

"The best thing was the sharing of experience with other makerspaces from different areas. We started to collect experiences with offering trainings to be able to generate income. The population here is not so open to new technology, but curiosity is growing."

Michael Danquah from Design and Technology Institute in Ghana

reports that the OCBM supported implementing more structured revenue-generating activities.

"It guided us in creating an online training model for 3D modeling, which helps us expand access to our offerings and attract a broader range of users... It has also helped us refine our approach to community engagement by offering new models like Startup Support."

Mary Nyamanga of FabLab Winam in Kenya

explains how the OCBM helped to re-evaluate the current business model.

"The OCBM has resulted in re-evaluating our current business model. We are considering implementing complementary models, where we have come up with a price list for different packages, which will help in addressing scalability and financial sustainability."

Through mentorship, co-creation, and an adaptable toolkit, the OCBM can help to transform makerspaces into financially resilient, impactful hubs for innovation. For further information visit LocalEconomies.org or contact anna@manufacturingchange.org.

Lessons learnt:

The resource will be further sustained and extended after the end of the mAKE project. Several users of the catalogue have suggested the addition of some case studies to help them understand different ways the same business model can be implemented in practice. Work has started to gather appropriate examples, and the intention is to add case studies to the online OCBM during 2025 under the lead of IOP. Both mentors and mentees have also stated that they see a lot of benefit from creating opportunities for meaningful exchange among and between the mentees based on the content of the OCBM. Thus, we are experimenting with different formats to allow for those exchanges to happen. The OCBM is also part of the mAKE MOOC. The process of mentoring makerspaces to use the OCBM allowed us to understand where there are common gaps in skills that would enable them to make better use of the catalogue. As a result, the mAKE MOOC will integrate video training materials in various market analysis and other relevant techniques to use the OCBM most effectively. Also, the new African Makerspace organization – named African Makerspace Ecosystem – and incorporated in South Africa at the end of 2024, will offer support functions to enable makerspaces to implement business models from the OCBM.

3.2 Venture Building and Business Development programme

The Venture Building and Business Development programme aimed to engage with 20 companies (startups and SMEs) in Europe and Africa, providing personalised one-on-one support tailored to each company's specific needs. In addition, a train-the-trainer programme was established with 14+ trainers from DIHs/makerspaces, offering practical advisory sessions to enhance their expertise in supporting startups and SMEs based on the created Venture Building Handbook.

3.2.1. The venture building programme

Outputs:

The mAKE venture building programme offered more than 130 hours of venture building support to 20 companies, which were selected from 53 applying companies based on the GreenTec Success Matrix and a ranking of the mAKE high-level Stakeholder Jury.

In an initial needs assessment with each company specific areas for improvement were identified and a roadmap elaborated. Thereafter, each of the companies was provided with one-on-one sessions tailored to their unique requirements, on topics such as business model refinement, financial analysis, valuation, prospecting, marketing, and distribution strategies. Two pitch training sessions were offered to participants, one digital pitch event was organized for all companies. The 10 top performing companies, selected based on their investor readiness and consistent efforts throughout the program, were invited in May 2024 to an investors trip to Cairo to participate in the EU mAKE Pitch Event. During this week they took part in the

Startup Without Border Summit with 1:1 investor matchmaking and in networking events with international startups, investors and development agencies such as GIZ.

Figure 1: Startup Without Border Summit

Figure 2: Ecosystem Night with international investors

To further enhance their readiness, the startups attending the Cairo trip received an in-person pitch training session, tailored to the specific conditions of the EU mAKE pitch event. Responding to their expressed interest in networking and community-building opportunities, we also organized a self-paid visit to the Pyramids of Gizeh, providing a platform for informal connections among the participants.

Outcomes:

Business growth and networking opportunities were the main expectations of participants at the beginning of the Venture Building programme. The feedback of the 20 participants at the end of the programme shows the great impact in this regard.

- They had significantly enhanced their ability to deliver compelling pitches to investors, resulting in increased interest and potential funding opportunities.
- The programme has enabled them to focus more sharply on essential activities, leading to more efficient and effective business operations.
- Through the networking opportunities provided, participants have built valuable connections with investors and fellow entrepreneurs, fostering collaboration and support.
- The programme has driven product iteration and the integration of advanced technologies, such as artificial intelligence, ensuring that participants remain competitive and innovative. A notable strategic shift has been the increased emphasis on customer acquisition over extensive fundraising efforts, aligning business development with long-term growth and sustainability objectives.

All these achievements underscore the transformative impact of the programme on participants' ventures.

Feedback Survey Quotes about the venture building program and Cairo investor trip:

- "The network of investors and the untapped opportunities of the MENA Region, the brilliant founders in the Cohort and warmth of the Greentec Capital Team."
- "I met other founders with whom I have remained in touch, and we have been a support to one another."
- "Amazing, lovely people in our cohort and lots of opportunities for growth. Honest feedback from investors."
- "Now I have mastered my pitch to investors as a result of this programme"
- "We will be more resilient and focused in scaling our operations"

A table that provides a summary of main outputs and outcomes related to the Venture Building programme can be found in [Annex 1](#).

Lessons learnt:

- The experience from the Venture Building program highlights the importance of targeted investor matching and fundraising, including both in-person and digital pitch events.
- Organizing face-to-face investor trips allows delegations of investors to engage more deeply with the companies and ecosystem and thus significantly enhance connections and support.

3.2.2. Venture building Handbook and ToT

Outputs:

The mAKE venture building handbook is a guide for entrepreneurs, venture builders, and makerspace managers, outlining 12 critical steps for launching and growing scalable businesses – from idea generation to market research, product development, and networking. It aimed at transforming makerspaces and DIHs into powerful venture builders, supporting entrepreneurs in developing sustainable, impactful businesses. The venture building handbook was launched in January 2024 and provided as downloadable file on the mAKE website. A French version was published in April 2024. **The English version of the handbook was downloaded 330 times only between Oct 20th, 2024, and Jan 30th, 2025 with numbers steadily increasing. The French version was downloaded 97 times in the same time.**

The handbook was also one of the core elements of the Venture Building Train-the-Trainer (ToT) program, that involved 25 makerspace experts from Europe and Africa (out of 76 applicants) in 6 interactive workshops, held on Business Models, Financial Analysis for Non-Financial Managers and on Marketing and Distribution. Homeworks and supportive course material such as presentations and templates were used to equip the students not only with foundational but also more in-depth knowledge.

The aim of this training was to build the participants' capacity to support startups and SMEs in der makerspaces. The feedback collected from the ToT participants via questionnaires helped to understand the usefulness and applicability of both, the ToT and the venture building handbook.

Outcomes:

The aim of the venture building handbook was to equip startups, SMEs, makerspaces and DIHs with an understanding of business fundamentals needed to run successful enterprises and attract potential investors. It showed that the handbook was perceived as highly useful by the involved makerspaces and business representatives in this regard. Handbook users highlighted the clear way each concept was presented and thus made easy to understand by readers, making it a perfect guide to get involved in venture building. Again, it was stressed that most of the makerspace activities are centered on making and building, but with the knowledge of the handbook, makerspaces are equipped with the knowledge on how to take innovations successfully into business.

Feedback quotes from the venture building handbook:

"This book turned out to be a true all-in-one gem! The instructions are clear and straightforward, making each concept refreshingly easy to grasp. It's the perfect go-to guide for me."

“It has given me the knowledge about venture building which I never knew before, Most of our Fablab activities are much more on making and building, but with this knowledge is how we take those Innovations into business.”

“The focus on user-centric design was eye-opening. It emphasized understanding the customer journey deeply, which has inspired me to conduct more thorough customer feedback sessions and adjust our solutions accordingly.”

“The Venture Building Handbook is enriched with insights that resonate with African businesses. I am still reading and excited to learn from the book that leveraging our local resources like talents can be an easy and best way of not just generating but validating the feasibility of an idea.”

Also, the ToT received very positive feedback. Trainees found the content delivery highly engaging and praised the energy, motivation, and responsiveness of the lecturers, who created an interactive and inclusive environment. The well-structured modules and carefully prepared sessions stood out, with participants valuing the detailed content and the quality of the provided materials. The trainees planned to apply their new knowledge in various ways to support and enhance the growth of startups within makerspaces. First, they wanted to offer tailored mentorship for startup founders, hub managers, and trainers, focusing on 1-on-1 sessions and fostering community networking events to strengthen connections and offer targeted guidance.

Another approach was working on makerspaces' own business models first and using the experience from this initial work to guide and coach other organizations and businesses. The goal of ToT participants is to develop sustainable business models and strategies, incorporating new expertise and technologies, such as adding machinery to increase capabilities, and ultimately helping innovators turn their ideas into viable businesses

A table that provides a summary of main outputs and outcomes related to the Venture Building Handbook (VBH) and ToTs can be found in [Annex 1](#).

Community Voices: Participants' feedback on the Venture Building ToT and Handbook

African European Maker
Innovation Ecosystem

Makerspaces as Catalysts for Business Growth with the mAKE Venture Building Programme

As worldwide hubs of creativity and innovation, makerspaces have the potential of transforming into powerful venture builders, supporting entrepreneurs in developing sustainable, impactful businesses. To strengthen this shift, GreenTec Capital Africa Foundation, developed a **Venture Building Programme and Handbook for makerspaces, digital innovation hubs, startups and SMEs.**

A Comprehensive Venture Building Toolkit

The Venture Building Handbook serves as a practical guide for entrepreneurs, venture builders, and makerspace managers. It outlines 12 critical steps for launching and growing scalable businesses — from idea generation to market research, product development, and networking. This structured approach provides entrepreneurs with both the strategic and operational skills needed for sustainable growth.

"The Venture Building Handbook has given me knowledge about venture building which I never knew before. Most of our Fablab activities are much more on making and building, but with this knowledge, we can now take those innovations into business." – Fablab Manager from Tanzania

12 steps for Venture Builders

1. Idea Generation and Validation	7. Legal and Regulatory Compliance
2. Market Research	8. Sales and Marketing Strategies
3. Business Model Development	9. Scaling and Growth
4. Product Development	10. Networking and Mentorship
5. Team Building and Leadership	11. Exit Strategies
6. Fundraising and financial management	12. Case Studies and Real-World Examples

Access the the Venture Building Handbook in English and French:
makeafricaeu.org
english

french

African European Maker
Innovation Ecosystem

Community Voices – Venture Building in Action

The handbook places a strong emphasis on user-centric design, a perspective that resonates deeply with entrepreneurs striving to address local needs and challenges.

"The focus on user-centric design was eye-opening. It emphasized understanding the customer journey deeply, inspiring me to conduct thorough customer feedback sessions and adjust our solutions accordingly." – Fablab Manager from Kenya

The handbook's emphasis on leveraging local resources has also sparked new insights.

"The handbook is enriched with insights that resonate with African businesses... leveraging our local resources, like talents, can be an easy and best way of not just generating but validating the feasibility of an idea." – Fablab Manager from Ghana

It provides makerspaces, entrepreneurs and startups with a frame for self-reflection, personal and corporate development.

"With this new knowledge, I intend to tailor support strategies for startups in makerspaces through 1-on-1 mentorship with founders, hub managers, and trainers. This approach will strengthen connections and foster an ecosystem where startups can access vital resources and collaborative opportunities for growth." – Trainer and Innovator from Tanzania

The handbook also serves as a testing ground for refining one's own business models before bringing these strategies to clients and community members.

"I liked the training content on Financial Analysis and Business Models best and will improve our current model of operations as a result of this knowledge." – Fablab Manager from Tanzania

"I will be my own test case first, fine-tuning the business model for my Hub. With that experience, I will then bring this approach to the organisations and businesses I mentor, coach, and train." – FabLab Manager from Ethiopia

A Path Forward for Makerspaces as Venture Builders

This pillar of the mAKE Venture Building Programme is supporting makerspaces to evolve into venture-building hubs that stimulate local economies and support sustainable business development. If you are interested, find more info on: makeafricaeu.org

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101016858

Lessons learnt:

- Financial topics are particularly challenging for some participants and highlights the need for future training programs that dedicate time to this critical subject while considering participants' time constraints. Incorporating more peer-to-peer learning methods could address this challenge, e.g. organising breakout rooms that allow participants applying their learnings collectively before reconvening in the larger group. There is a need for discussions and dialogue that foster the understanding of different perspectives from investors, founders, and makers transitioning into entrepreneurship. This approach helps to identify common grounds and create deeper appreciation for the interconnectedness of social impact and entrepreneurial success.
- Building upon the existing OCBM, future venture building sessions could equip makerspaces and hubs with the necessary tools to not only develop sustainable business models but also skills on how to run a business. In addition, trainees expressed the need for a support platform for key challenges faced by makerspaces and their ventures in emerging markets, such as funding, equipment sourcing, staff training, and operational management.

During events like AfriLabs and mAkErverse, the strong interest in the VBH highlighted the pressing need for venture building support within the makerspace and innovation ecosystem. The VBH itself is proven to be a valuable resource which can be seen in the feedback from Venture Building & ToT participants and has thus been integrated in the mAKE MOOC, where additional training material will support learners in using it most efficiently.

3.3 Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme and matchmaking activities

3.3.1. Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme

Outputs:

The Makers-in-Residency (MiR) program has successfully connected African and European makers, fostering a unique blend of knowledge sharing and collaborative innovation. Receiving a total of 104 maker and 29 makerspace applications showcases the interest and need in such collaboration programs. Due to visa delays, rescheduling, cancellations and more, multiple attempts to pursue the MiR have been made, involving the European makerspace Network Vulva for outreach and matchmaking purposes. Six makers were ultimately selected for the final implementation of the program (MiR 2.0 and 3.0) based on the High-Level Stakeholder Jury rating.

In this program, 4 emerging innovators from Egypt, Tanzania, and Rwanda, were provided with a one-month residency in European makerspaces in Belgium, France and Spain. Each maker elevated their prototype to the next level while benefiting from direct mentorship, access to advanced equipment, and an inspiring environment. Additionally, before traveling to their final residency destinations, they joined the re:publica, a

conference on digital society, as well as the GiG Gathering giving them the opportunity to network with innovation ecosystem stakeholders.

Four completed their residencies in European makerspaces, whereas one was redirected to Cape Town due to ongoing visa challenges, and another, unable to travel due to eligibility constraints, was supported remotely with materials and expert mentoring sessions.

The maker who was scheduled to travel to Cape Town faced additional visa delays and could not attend in person. However, he worked closely with his expert from FabLab Copenhagen to advance his prototype of a digital stethoscope. Together, they explored market interest for the device (digital stethoscope), laying the groundwork for potentially creating a business around the innovation.

Figure 3: KPIs of MiR

Outcomes:

While mAKE faced some considerable challenges with organizing this ambitious exchange program, the outcomes show the huge impact it had on both – European hosts and African makers alike. The exchange was an important learning experience for all involved – while the makers got to know new machines and infrastructures not available in their African makerspaces and benefited from the conceptual and technical support of the European makerspace teams. The European makerspace hosts were inspired by the innovative mindset of the young makers and the values of openness and cultural exchange that the MiR brought into their spaces. The community voices show more of these impacts:

Community Voices: Makers and Hosts Experiences from the MiR exchange programme

MAKE African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem

The “Makers in Residency”–Programme Sparks Innovation and Collaboration between African and European Makers

The Makers in Residency (MiR) programme has successfully connected African and European makers, fostering a unique blend of knowledge sharing and collaborative innovation. In 2024, the MiR programme supported four emerging hardware innovators from Egypt, Tanzania, and Rwanda, providing a one-month residency in European makerspaces. Each maker worked on ground-breaking projects while benefiting from direct mentorship, access to advanced equipment, and an inspiring environment.

“This initiative aims to break down barriers, create new ideas, and build essential networks between continents.”
 ---- Fabienne Kirchof, GreenTec Capital Africa Foundation ----

Martine, a maker from Rwanda hosted in Belgium, focused on a sustainable solution to reduce material costs for makers by recycling plastic bottles to create affordable 3D printer filament.

“The timeline was tight, but with the Liege team’s support, we combined our efforts to make it happen.” --- Martine Basaninyage, Makerspace Westerwelle Startup Haus Kigali, Rwanda ---

Martine’s hosts witnessed her dedication and ingenuity,
“We learned so much from her resourcefulness and resilience — she’s building amazing solutions with far fewer resources than we’re used to.”
 --- Loic, Hackerspace Liege, Belgium ---

Asem, a maker from Egypt hosted in France, brought a sense of international community to La Bricothèque Fablab, engaging with local members and sharing his project’s vision and knowledge.

“Asem’s openness to share his work and life experiences made our Fablab feel part of a global network. We saw a natural exchange of ideas and cultural understanding”
 --- Olivier, La Bricothèque, France ---

“My impression about this program is positive and eye opening, as someone who has never been to Europe it was amazing seeing such cool places like the textile lab”.
 --- Asem Kamal, maker and content creator, Egypt ---

MAKE African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem

Meanwhile, Leonard, a maker from Tanzania hosted in Spain, pursued his vision to build a nano-satellite prototype to inspire African students and makers in STEM. During his residency at Fablab Barcelona, Leonard expanded his network and honed his technical skills with new equipment.

“This programme brought me closer to new knowledge, and I had hands-on experience with different machines that sparked ideas on how I can bring similar technology to Tanzania.”
 --- Leonard Shayo, founder of the aerospace startup Olspace ---

His host, Santi from Fablab Barcelona, was equally inspired, noting Leonard’s unstoppable drive: *“He came in saying, ‘I have to learn as much as I can; I want to send a rocket to the moon!’ His determination was infectious.”*
 --- Santi, Fablab Barcelona ---

Witness, a Tanzanian maker hosted in France, reflected on how the residency inspired her project management approach and technical work.

“I have been impressed by the makerspace, the organization, the workshops and overall management. This creates a truly inspiring environment for anyone to get creative.”
 --- Witness Shingali, Twende Social Innovation Center, Tanzania ---

Although she felt that one month was limited for a complex prototype, Witness returned to Tanzania with a strong foundation, sketches, and collaborative documentation to drive her project forward. This residency programme has not only equipped African makers with new tools and skills but also brought fresh perspectives and cultural insights to the European hosts.

“We documented everything to support Witness’s ongoing work in Tanzania. The collaboration doesn’t end here; we’ll stay connected to help her team scale up.”
 --- Matthieu, Ecocentre, France ---

“Through these transformative exchanges, the MiR programme has strengthened a global network of makers committed to using their skills to address real-world challenges, demonstrating the powerful impact of cross-continental collaboration in the maker community.”
 --- Kirstin Wiedow, Global Innovation Gathering ---

Further information on makeafricaeu.org

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101016858

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016858.

A table that provides a summary of main outputs and outcomes related to MiR can be found in [Annex 1](#).

Lessons learnt:

The feedback sessions and feedback reports provided important lessons learned on how to optimize the exchange program, which are shared in an extra report and can be summarized as:

A key learning from MiR 1.0 was the difficulty of aligning makers with suitable makerspaces, considering factors such as machinery, expertise, community dynamics, and language. To address this challenge the collaboration with the Vulca Network (<https://vulca.eu> – a key facilitator of European makerspace) proved to facilitate this task and showed how important in-person connections are in achieving successful matches. The collaboration with Vulca has also eased the application process for European makerspaces, as they have been briefed by their known and trusted organisation about projects and application procedures.

In terms of programme design, flexibility in duration is necessary to adapt to the requirements of different projects, varying in intensities and durations, and to consider the makers' individual life situations, such as family commitments, student responsibilities, or employment obligations. Potential changes in individual situations can also affect the ability of makers to participate in a project, especially if visa procedures take very long.

The biggest issue was related to the difficulties that African passport-holders currently face in receiving visas from European countries, which has also been documented in a separate policy brief (see Chapter 8: Community Engagement for more information). It took significant time and effort and strongly hindered the idea of facilitating in-person interaction by African makers with European makerspace contexts.

There are some key recommendations for exchange programmes, that GT, GIG and Vulca have elaborated and shared for other Residency Planners & Funders.

- **Contracts and Deliverables:** Establish contracts that clearly define project deliverables, timelines, and responsibilities. A well-outlined project structure helps prevent misunderstandings, as seen in the example with Joseph's project, where initial expectations differed from final project actions.
- **Visa Planning:** For makers coming from countries with complex visa requirements, include ample lead time for visa approvals. Inquiring about other pending visas could help avoid delays related to passport availability.
- **Matchmaking Resources:** Allocate funds to support network partners like Vulca, enabling a more thorough matchmaking process. Early alignment on project goals ensures both the maker and expert have a shared vision from the outset.
- **Pre-Residency Design Support:** Consider funding the maker and the expert during the preparation phase, encouraging them to work on design and planning tasks ahead of the residency. This advance work facilitates smoother project progression on-site.

- **Advance Planning and Timeline:** Begin residency planning and application calls at least six months in advance. This longer timeline allows for effective preparation and helps accommodate visa processing, material sourcing, and clear budgeting.
- **Rural Areas:** Consider hosting two residencies simultaneously to mitigate challenges faced in remote locations. This approach ensures better resource allocation, while also facilitating networking and community engagement for participants.

3.3.2. Further matchmaking activities

GT organized 28 Funder-to-Funder events that connected European and African innovators to collaboratively co-create and co-found new ventures. Given the challenge that intercontinental ventures need time for trust to establish, the F2F events focused on offering community-based events as an initial platform for connecting and co-creation.

Figure 4: KPIs of Matchmaking events

The objective of the 2 Business-to-Business matchmaking events was to facilitate the creation of meaningful partnerships and provide a platform for startups to discuss common challenges, share knowledge, and explore potential collaborations across sectors.

Figure 5: Business-to-Business matchmaking

A table that provides a summary of main outputs and outcomes related to the further matchmaking can be found in [Annex 1](#).

Lessons learnt:

- The Founder-to-Founder matchmaking initiative highlighted the importance of trust-building, particularly in creating informal, community-based events where innovators could share ideas, discuss challenges, and co-create solutions. These events helped to bridge geographical and cultural gaps and laid the foundation for long-term partnerships. Though investors did not directly invest during the matchmaking events, their role in supporting ventures was recognized as critical for future growth. Investors offer valuable guidance on structuring businesses and scaling operations, making them essential in transforming collaborative ideas into viable ventures.
- Moreover, the initiative emphasized the importance of cross-sector collaboration, where stakeholders from the public, private, and non-profit sectors work together to strengthen innovation ecosystems. Bringing together diverse stakeholders helps foster impactful collaborations that drive sustainable development.
- The primary challenge highlighted throughout the business-to-business events was the financial constraints faced by early-stage startups, particularly those in the fundraising phase. These limitations restrict their ability to fully engage in collaborative projects. Despite these challenges, the events demonstrated the significant value of strategic networking and partnership discussions as crucial tools to overcome such financial barriers.

3.4 Innovative Funding Mechanisms

Based on five interviews, one workshop and all the experiences made in WP1, some important recommendations for **innovative funding mechanisms** for makerspaces and DIHs were elaborated.

- Many investors are unfamiliar with the concept and impact of makerspaces and FabLabs specifically. To address this challenge, a central focus of future activities should be on raising awareness about the value and impact of makerspaces through online and offline pitch events where startups associated with makerspaces could present their innovations directly to investors.
- Visits to makerspaces should be a part of structured investor trips as well as impact events to highlight the broader social and economic contributions of makerspaces and their ventures. The budget for travel and accommodations has to be foreseen to finance these visits and create strong investor-makerspace networks. The project revealed that makerspaces often struggle to secure funding through traditional means, operating on limited resources and prioritizing shared access to tools and knowledge. This necessitates the exploration of innovative and community-centric funding models. Also, alternative mechanisms such as grants, corporate sponsorships, and partnerships with educational institutions emerged as vital strategies. These models align with the ethos of openness and collaboration that defines makerspaces and provide sustainable avenues for growth and impact
- Another critical insight was the importance of leveraging partnerships and networks, both locally and globally. Collaborations with international organizations, local businesses, and schools or universities can bring in not only financial support but also access to expertise, advanced tools, and broader networks. Such partnerships play a pivotal role in ensuring the sustainability and scalability of makerspaces, enabling them to continue driving innovation and creating opportunities for diverse communities

A table that provides a summary of main outputs and outcomes related to the Innovative Funding mechanism can be found in [Annex 1](#).

4. Hub ecosystem and policy frameworks (WP2)

WP2 aimed at improving connections between DIHs/makerspaces and public sector actors as well as local political decision-makers, so as to build recognition and favourable policies in support of national and regional startup ecosystems.

Outputs:

1. **Case studies on seven DIH/makerspace associations**, with a specific focus on their engagement in policy making processes (D2.1: Report on National and Regional Hub Associations including 7 Documented Case Studies and Comparative Analyses, completed at the end of Y1 (M12, January 2023). **A common policy agenda** with a strong engagement of the makerspace ecosystem. A series of 18 sessions (workshops and focus group interviews) were conducted, engaging a diverse group of 69 participants (26 of the participants representing African DIHs/makerspaces and 43 representing European DIH/makerspaces) to collect the requirements and needs of

DIHs/makerspaces, in terms of barriers and enablers faced, in both Africa and Europe. This Common Policy Agenda and Recommendations for Policy Makers, was formulated and put to discussion in a mAkE webinar with 26 participants from across Africa and Europe. A **public version of the common policy agenda** that includes relevant case studies aligned with the five recommendations outlined in the document. To ensure the targeted groups (policymakers, government officials, local and international organizations, institutions, makers, and the public) who are expected to play a critical role in realizing the recommendations were well represented and explicitly mentioned in the policy and associated materials. Strategies for disseminating the common policy were also developed to guide various groups in supporting the agenda.

2. In terms of policy dissemination, a methodological plan was established to ensure involvement in events related to innovation and policy. This approach meant that dissemination was not solely focused on a bottom-up strategy but also incorporated a top-down approach. The policy was shared during one-on-one meetings, workshops, and public gatherings. A total of 11 events were attended by at least one member of the mAkE team to share the common policy agenda. Of these 11 events, five were organized in Africa, four in Europe, and two were conducted on virtual platforms. Across these events, over 400 participants and stakeholders were engaged, including more than 40 government officials. The events ensured that government officials had the opportunity to receive firsthand information about the policy and explore ways they could support its implementation. Since D2.3 emphasizes “minister meets maker,” all the events organized included makers who shared their stories—highlighting successes, failures, challenges, and opportunities with policymakers. These interactions allowed policymakers to provide advice to makers and continue the dialogue and collaboration beyond the events.
3. The **policy agenda was downloaded 368 times only between Oct 20th, 2024, and Jan 31th, 2024, the 2-pager policy brief was downloaded 78 times** in the same period.

Outcome:

The work on the policy agenda brought light to an underserved topic in the makerspace ecosystem – the way how political decision makers could best support makerspaces and DIHs and how relationships with political actors could be initiated and successfully maintained.

The Common Policy Agenda recommendations provided a common ground to start a dialogue between makerspace/DIHs representatives and political actors at regional, national and international level. It helped to establish first relationships and occasions for experience sharing based on the five recommendations and supported makers and political decision makers to get to know each other’s viewpoint and needs. We could observe an increased commitment from government officials to support the agenda, as evidenced by their participation in events.

The events provided also a good occasion to collect feedback on the policy agenda where some community voices are presented in the following document.

Community Voices: Feedback of on the Policy Recommendations

MAKE African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem

Policy Recommendations for Makerspaces Gain Ground with Global Policymakers

"These policy recommendations have not only attracted the attention of local government representatives, makerspaces, founders and NGOs. They have also charted a clear way forward for makerspaces. Through ongoing workshops and dialogues, this living document serves as a tool to foster collaboration, innovation, and sustainable development within the local and global maker ecosystems."

--- Joseph Agyina, Internet of Production ---

In 2023, the mAKE project engaged with 69 stakeholders (26 from Africa, 43 from Europe), including makers, founders, educators, managers, and community members from diverse makerspaces, to co-create a set of **POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS**.

Throughout 2024, the policy recommendations have been presented to both policymakers and makerspaces at various events. Feedback from these engagements highlights the growing interest in implementing and expanding the recommendations.

"We engaged for one year with makers and stakeholders within the African and European ecosystems to gain insights into the barriers and enablers influencing their work and to explore how governments at various levels can recognise and support makerspaces."

--- Freda Yamorti Gbande, Fab City Foundation---

During the Ghana Hubs Network's general meeting 2023, the policy recommendations were presented to a diverse group of stakeholders — including government representatives such as the Director of Communication from the National Entrepreneurship and Innovation Programme (NEIP), a GIZ representative, the Dean of Languages at Takoradi Technical University (TTU), and others from the Ghana Association of Industry and the Ghana National Youth Employment Agency.

MAKE African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem

5 Policy Recommendations ...

- 01 Leverage the potential of makerspaces by collaborating on national projects that focus on capacity building for youth and entrepreneurs, while promoting locally made products.
- 02 Create funding initiatives to provide resources for makerspaces to implement research and innovation projects.
- 03 Endorse maker programs and courses, which are funded by the government and aimed at local communities.
- 04 Integrate makerspaces into school curricula, particularly focusing on Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics (STEAM) education.
- 05 Recognize makerspaces as critical infrastructure for local manufacturing.

... and Community Voices

"Establishing government partnerships and collaborating on national projects could provide makerspaces with opportunities to contribute their expertise and resources toward addressing societal challenges, while also raising their profile and influence."

"Implementing dedicated funding programmes would allow makerspaces to enhance their capabilities, invest in critical equipment, and drive forward innovation projects."

"Recommendations #3 and #4 regarding endorsing maker programs/courses and integrating makerspace activities into formal education curricula could significantly boost awareness, access, and sustainability for these facilities."

"From a global perspective it stimulates open source knowledge exchange and proliferation of technologies."

The recommendations, including more detailed explanations and good practice examples from around the world can be accessed under: makeafricaeu.org

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101016858

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016858.

A table that provides a summary of main outputs and outcomes related to the work with policy makers can be found in [Annex 1](#).

Lessons learnt:

Accessing policymakers presents a significant challenge due to bureaucratic hurdles and their limited availability. Securing their attention requires navigating multiple layers of protocols, often delaying opportunities for engagement. In addition to bureaucratic hurdles, policymakers are very often not aware of the maker movement and the impact it has on local communities in terms of supporting innovation and business capacity. Thus, advocacy efforts often required significant time to explain the ecosystem, its relevance, and alignment with policy goals to stakeholders.

On the other side, makerspaces and DIHs are very much focused on the making and creating impact for their communities, facing reduced capacities and experience in advocacy work towards political decision makers. Many rely on founders and managers to handle multiple roles, including product development, fundraising, and community engagement.

To address these challenges, we see the crucial role of global and national network organizations to strengthen synergies within and across ecosystems, drive awareness campaigns and consistent engagement to build understanding and support towards policy makers.

We also recognise maker gatherings as pivotal for innovation, collaboration, and aligning makerspaces with policy goals. Events such as Maker Faire, FABx, Africa Makerspace Ecosystem Gathering, Re:publica and Vulca seminars provide formal platforms for makers and policymakers to engage in meaningful dialogues. Both, networking organizations and networking gatherings could support makerspaces facing operational limitations due to small teams and constrained budgets.

Existing relationships with policymakers are an important step to facilitate the advocacy work and create valuable opportunities to share and discuss the policy recommendations. If engaged, policymakers demonstrated promising developments in supporting makerspaces. As an example, in Ghana, the Ministry of Environment, Science, and Technology actively collaborates with initiatives like the Ghana Hubs Network and international partners such as Japan International Cooperation Agency JICA to develop makerspaces and promote prototyping.

However, systemic barriers persist, including competition with large industries for funding and support. These challenges highlight the need for tailored policies that recognize the unique contributions of makerspaces to local innovation and production.

Finally, we observed that the interest in the Common Policy Agenda from European makerspaces was less pronounced, potentially due to the advanced state of the maker movement in the region or differing priorities. Strengthening connections with European Digital Innovation Hubs remains crucial for fostering mutual and sustainable collaborations. While initial efforts established valuable relationships, further initiatives are needed to bridge the gap between African and European maker ecosystems.

5. Open education, skill development and capacity building (WP3)

This work package (WP3) was dedicated to the training and up-skilling of DIHs/makerspaces and the makers, innovators, entrepreneurs, SMEs and startups they interact with.

5.1 Open Makerspace Toolkit and training of trainers

Outputs:

The Open Makerspace Toolkit, now available online, contains elements of existing open educational resources (OERs), and OERs created by the mAKE project, on how to set up, manage, equip and sustain different types of open, collaborative and innovative makerspaces. During the development of the Toolkit, we:

- Connected with external stakeholders via a survey to collect OERs. This survey is still open and has to date received 15 high-quality responses from external stakeholders.
- Collected and reviewed existing OERs that were potentially relevant to the Toolkit.
- Selected, for inclusion in the Toolkit, elements of existing OERs with strong relevance to the maker movement and/or social innovation.
- Selected, for inclusion in the Toolkit, elements of existing OERs created by the mAKE project.

The Open Makerspace Toolkit has been published, as an open access resource, on the Pressbooks platform, <https://pressbooks.pub>, which is an OER-focused platform that allows for easy updating of content. Using the Pressbooks platform makes the Toolkit a non-static, living resource that can grow and improve as more elements become available from external sources and from the work of mAKE consortium members. The Toolkit is available at <https://pressbooks.pub/omt4make>.

The Toolkit was downloaded 185 times only between Oct 20th, 2024, and Jan 30th, 2025 from the mAKE website. The online version was accessed 1312 times from Nov 2023 to Jan 2025.

Upon publication of the Toolkit, focus shifted towards the organisation of the training-of-trainers (ToT) activities that, in Y3, trained initial cohorts of DIH/makerspace-linked trainers in how to train others to use the Toolkit.

Overall, 5 ToTs were organised. The first ToT event took place in March 2024 at the premises of mAKE consortium member the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC) in Barcelona, in conjunction with a mAKE consortium meeting and hosted 12 participants. A second ToT event was held in May 2024 at Ongola Fablab in Yaoundé hosting 13 participants, the third ToT took place in Abidjan, Ivory Coast. This event, organized by H-Fablab and facilitated by Dodji Honou, was held on April 27, 2024. The event garnered significant interest from 10 participants, who valued the opportunity to deepen their understanding of the

unique challenges faced by makerspaces in the Ivorian context. The fourth ToT program, facilitated by Dodji Honou and held on June 1st, 2024 in Berlin during the re:publica makerspace gathering, was met with 10 participants. The last ToT session was held at Academic City University in Ghana during the Africa Open Science Hardware Summit on July 18, 2024. The session was led by Kwaku Effa Adu-Ampomah, who had received training on the OMT from Samuel Boadu Duah and attracted 29 participants.

In addition to training Toolkit users in their home countries, these initial cohorts of trained trainers are expected to conduct their own online and in-person train-the-trainers events, in order to extend the reach of training capacity for the Toolkit.

The evaluation of the Train-the-Trainer program for the Open Makerspace Toolkit (OMT) is essential to assess its effectiveness in achieving the desired learning objectives and ensuring continuous improvement. So far, 27 participants have completed the feedback surveys, including 17 who took part in the Ghana ToT, seven in the Cameroon ToT and three in the Côte d'Ivoire ToT.

Outcomes:

The feedback of ToT participants and ToT trainers revealed that:

- The *OpenMakerSpaces Toolkit* was a central element of the workshops, offering participants structured guidance on crucial aspects of makerspace operations. Modules on setup, communication, and business modelling provided practical tools for immediate adaptation and implementation.
- Both the toolkit and the ToT workshops were instrumental in empowering makerspaces with actionable knowledge and resources. They played a vital role in improving operations, fostering community engagement, and driving innovation within the maker ecosystem.
- Participants expressed confidence in applying the knowledge and skills gained during the workshops. The toolkit's clear and context-relevant recommendations ensured its accessibility and facilitated seamless integration into existing workflows.
- The ToT workshops inspired facilitators and participants to rethink their business models with a focus on sustainability and inclusivity. This motivation translated into efforts to enhance financial sustainability while ensuring broader community impact.
- The enthusiasm generated during the workshops encouraged participants to actively share the toolkit with peers. This ongoing promotion is expected to broaden its reach and amplify its impact across the maker communities in Cameroon, Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, and beyond.

A table that provides a summary of main outputs and outcomes related to the Open Makerspace Toolkit and the ToTs can be found in [Annex 1](#).

Lessons learnt

As reported in the Interim Evaluation Report (D7.2., submitted in M24) the overly ambitious projected numbers with respect to including existing OERs, and OERs created by the mAKE project, in the Toolkit have been adapted. It was determined that the emphasis needed to be on quality rather than quantity. Accordingly, we revised the OER targets downwards and identified 400 OERs with potential relevance for the toolkit, selected elements of approx. 80 OER to be included in the Toolkit and created 3 elements that were included in the Toolkit.

In addition, it was decided to implement the Makerspace Toolkit as an online version on the OER-focused Pressbooks platform, <https://pressbooks.com> to allow for rapid content additions and updates.

One obstacle of organising the ToT was ensuring that training sessions were accessible and inclusive to all members of the community, regardless of their prior experience, skill level, or location. One effective strategy involved integrating ToT training into existing initiatives and programs, rather than organizing separate, stand-alone events. This approach proved beneficial, as it facilitated training sessions led by previous ToT participants, fostering a sustainable and community-driven approach.

Further feedback and impact stories from the ToTs in Cameroon, Ghana and Ivory Coast are presented in the following Community Voices.

Community Voices on the Training-of-Trainers

MAKE African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem

Empowering Maker Communities: The Open Makerspace Toolkit and Training-of-Trainers Program

The mAKE project's **Training-of-Trainers (ToT) program** shows how education and innovation can come together to transform communities. Through the **Open Makerspace Toolkit (OMT)**, the program has empowered local leaders in Ghana, Cameroon, and Côte d'Ivoire to create vibrant hubs of creativity and learning, fostering STEM education and sustainability.

The **Open Makerspace Toolkit** provides structured, actionable guidance on key areas such as makerspaces setup, communication strategies, and business model development. The **Training-of-Trainers program** introduced participants in methodologies on how to train the usage of the Open Makerspace Toolkit in their local communities.

Access the Open Makerspace Toolkit in English or French under:

<https://makeafricaeu.org>

A Ripple Effect of Change

The Open Makerspace Toolkit and Training-of-Trainers program's impact goes beyond individual sessions:

- **Adaptability:** The OMT's flexible design has enabled its integration into diverse contexts.
- **Sustainability:** By fostering collaboration and equipping participants with practical tools, the program has ensured that knowledge and resources are continuously shared.
- **Community-Led Growth:** From Ghana to Cameroon and Côte d'Ivoire, trained facilitators have taken ownership, creating a ripple effect of innovation.

MAKE African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem

Ghana: Transforming Education with STEM Lab

In July 2024, Kweku Efa-Ampomah, a passionate advocate for STEM education, led a **Train-the-Trainer workshop** at the AfricaOSH Summit in Accra. Equipped with skills and resources from the Open Makerspace Toolkit and inspired by the workshop, Kweku facilitated others to bring innovation to the classroom.

- Kweku trained over **50 teachers** from **12 public schools** across Ghana, equipping them to manage 12 newly established STEM laboratories in senior high schools.
- The Open Makerspace Toolkit's comprehensive resources and standardized best practices play a pivotal role in **ensuring the sustainability and inclusivity** of these labs.
- These labs provide students with hands-on experience in 3D printing, robotics, and digital fabrication, fostering ideation and problem-solving.

"The Open Makerspace Toolkit has been instrumental in guiding me through setting up and managing makerspaces effectively, particularly in designing sustainable business models that align with our community's needs," Kweku shared.

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101016858

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016858.

Cameroon: Sustaining Innovation in Makerspaces

The Mboalob, a prominent makerspace in Yaoundé in Cameroon, has shown how the ToT program and Open Makerspace Toolkit can become a cornerstone of training and empowering local makers. Mboalob has seamlessly integrated the OMT into its operations.

- The ToT methodology is now part of **quarterly workshops**, serving as a tool for onboarding new members and sustaining engagement.
- Resulting in an increased **member participation** and improved **project quality**.

"By integrating the ToT methodology into our training programs and utilizing the OMT as a comprehensive resource, we've observed a significant increase in member engagement, a deeper understanding of key concepts, and a noticeable improvement in the quality of projects developed," said Stephane Fadanka, Executive Director of Mboalob.

Following the inaugural training in May 2024, facilitators such as **Fabrice Tei Jouet** (Africa Robot) and **Mohammed Basirou** (Ongola Fablab) have extended the program, hosting events that promote collaboration and innovation within their networks. This shows how the ToT and OMT resources are adopted and applied in new contexts by training participants.

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101016858

Côte d'Ivoire: Balancing Mission and Sustainability

In Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire, the ToT workshop held at HFabLab in April 2024 focused on leveraging makerspaces for socio-economic development.

- Participants explored innovative strategies to make makerspaces financially sustainable while remaining inclusive to the entire community.
- These discussions sparked new ideas on how makerspaces can balance their mission-driven goals with practical economic considerations.
- The workshop fostered collaboration among makers, innovators, and community leaders.

"This ToT was an exceptional opportunity to share knowledge and exchange ideas on developing the capacity of makerspaces, using the valuable training elements of the toolkit," said Dodji Honou, CEO of HFabLab.

For more information, please visit makeafricaeu.org

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101016858

5.2 MOOC

Outputs:

The [mAKE MOOC](#) is a dynamic and comprehensive online learning platform tailored to empower individuals and organizations operating within the maker ecosystem. The mAKE MOOC equips participants with the skills and resources necessary to thrive in an interconnected and innovation-driven environment, ultimately contributing to a robust and inclusive maker community. This platform is designed to serve a diverse audience, including:

1. Makers – Innovators and creators who utilize makerspaces to design, prototype, and produce innovative solutions.
2. Promoters of Makerspaces – Advocates and managers who aim to expand the reach and impact of makerspaces in fostering innovation and entrepreneurship.
3. Decision-Makers – Policymakers and stakeholders responsible for driving strategic development and support for the maker ecosystem.

The design of the mAKE-MOOC began in the 13th month of the mAKE project (April 2023) with an in-depth analysis of the various Learning Management System (LMS) solutions and platforms available. After evaluating these options based on criteria such as sustainability, robustness, and features, we chose Moodle for its strong advantages in terms of durability and versatility.

To ensure the sustainability of the MOOC, we focused on fostering the adoption of the platform by members of the mAKE project consortium. To this end, three dedicated meetings were held to present the platform to consortium members. Following these presentations, we invited them to complete a [Mooc Content Submission Form](#) based on the outputs and results of the mAKE project. This approach led to the creation of courses such as Policy Agenda and Venture Building Handbook.

The mAKE MOOC has produced several key outputs, positioning itself as a vital resource for the maker ecosystem. It offers structured courses focused on five core themes: organizational development, business and makerspaces, collaboration and opportunities, mediation between science and society for social innovation, and information and communication strategies. The platform serves as a repository of practical tools, methodologies, and best practices designed to empower participants with actionable insights. A unique feature of the MOOC is its shared learning environment, which allows other projects and organizations to host their own courses, significantly broadening its impact. By fostering engagement among African and European Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs), the platform has created a dynamic space for cross-regional interaction and collaboration.

The mAKE MOOC has been officially launched during a webinar held in [English](#) and [French](#) on Thursday 23 January, 2025. This online interactive event focused on the presentation of the MOOC, which includes a variety of courses amongst which:

Figure 6: Two modules of the mAKE MOOC

73 people attended the English version of the Webinar, 22 the French version. Overall, 68 people are registered to the MOOC after the two webinars.

Outcome:

The outcomes of the mAKE MOOC reflect its mission to build a robust and interconnected maker ecosystem. It empowers diverse stakeholders, including makers, promoters of makerspaces, and decision-makers, with essential skills and knowledge to drive innovation and strategic growth. The platform strengthens collaboration by creating a joint learning space for African and European DIHs, fostering the exchange of ideas and best practices. Additionally, it enhances accessibility by making educational resources available to a wide audience, contributing to a more inclusive maker community. Through its focus on sustainability and scalability, the MOOC ensures long-term relevance and impact, supporting continuous innovation and development across regions. Moreover, its flexible and scalable infrastructure ensures that it remains adaptable to future projects and initiatives.

It is in this capacity that the platform is already hosting courses from another project piloted by IOPA, one of mAKE's consortium members. The "[La Forge d'Adaptations Nord-Sud](#)" project, led by Climate Change Lab (CC Lab), is also interested in transforming its ongoing documentation and making it available on our mAKE-MOOC platform. In addition, the Local Accessible Urban Digital Sustainable Factories (LAUDS) project, co-funded by the European Union, is considering using the mAKE MOOC for their training purpose.

Lessons learnt:

The process of designing and implementing the MOOC as part of the mAKE project has provided valuable insights:

Learning content development

Developing the learning content for the mAKE MOOC revealed the importance of tailored support for contributors. While consortium members were enthusiastic about participating, varying levels of familiarity with Moodle and online course design presented challenges. To address this, we combined the initial content submission form developed by APSOHA with structured sheets provided by IAAC. This integration

allowed us to streamline the content development process and achieve the high-quality results that defined the mAKE MOOC's final content.

A Sustainable pedagogical approach based on active participation

From the outset, we prioritized the active involvement and engagement of consortium members. Early in the project, dedicated meetings were organized to facilitate their understanding of the MOOC and foster a sense of ownership. This collaborative approach aligned the platform's development with the consortium's objectives and encouraged members to propose course ideas, significantly enriching the MOOC's content.

Iterative development and feedback

Adopting an iterative development approach has been instrumental in ensuring continuous refinement of both the platform and the courses. Feedback from users played a central role in this process, guiding improvements to the MOOC's usability and content quality.

To systematically gather participant insights, we designed a questionnaire using Slido, which focuses on the following key aspects:

1. Ease of navigation on the mAKE MOOC platform and suggestions for improvement.
2. Clarity and usefulness of resources (e.g., videos, readings, materials), along with suggestions for additional content or courses.
3. Likelihood of recommending the MOOC to colleagues or peers.
4. Recommendations for enhancing the platform's accessibility and inclusivity for a global audience.

Preliminary feedback from Slido highlights valuable insights into user experiences and potential areas for improvement. These findings will be analyzed further to ensure that the MOOC remains accessible, effective, and aligned with the diverse needs of its learners.

6. Distributed manufacturing network (WP4)

This work package (WP4) aimed to foster distributed manufacturing among DIHs/makerspaces by prototyping and supporting adoption of digital infrastructures that enable sharing of skills, machinery, and contracts within DIH/makerspace networks.

6.1 People and Skills Specification (PSS) and Maker Passport prototype

Outputs:

The work on the maker passport started with a conceptual phase under strong involvement of the makerspace community via a PSS Working group, aiming to develop the People and Skills Specification (PSS) which provides a framework for creating a record of skills and training for a maker to showcase his expertise.

In year 3, the work focused on the research of systems where the PSS can be applied to develop a digital maker passport that will detain certifications and training of makers. We identified two methods as systems that could serve for creating the skills certifications held in a digital maker passport: 1) Community-based authentication and 2) Badging systems.

To test the concept and receive feedback on usefulness and applicability, the maker passport has been tested in two use cases: Innovative Manufacturing and REFFAO. In both cases we learned that the maker passport is an uncontested opportunity for both, individual makers who want to participate in distributed production processes, and networks of makerspaces that wish to drive distributed production.

Proof-of-concept: Innovative Manufacturing in Africa project

In this project the makers, to participate in distributed production, had to sign up for the maker passport, using a maker passport signup form. Three trials of distributed manufacturing were run, and the makers who initially enrolled with a maker passport were directly contacted to participate in the next rounds of trials, according to their skills, experience and location. Forty-five (45) makers signed up for the maker passport, as reported in the last impact assessment report. The report of these trials was shared with the PSS Working group to continue the research on the development of a maker passport prototype. An important outcome from this experience was that the maker passport needs to be used offline for areas that may experience low to no bandwidth or intermittent loss of access to the internet.

Proof-of-concept: REFFAO, West African network of FabLabs

The application of the maker passport within the REFFAO network is a great example. We have been working with Dodji Honou of H-fablab to review current training programmes and mapping credential issuance processes to pre-existing certificates. During interviews and co-working sessions he shared the following values they see in having maker passports:

- ◆ Share expertise and knowledge with the network
- ◆ Ease and speed up the set-up of makers visit a space within the network
- ◆ Instore and create common certifications and trainings

Figure 7: Example of certification shared by H-FabLab

In year 3 we also worked on the **Maker Passport platform** (<https://maker-passport.fly.dev/profiles>). The maker passport platform was designed to help makers showcase their profiles, skills, and certifications (with issuance details and digital badges), location, and links to personal or professional websites, social media accounts, and projects. The platform aims to connect makers with potential collaborators or clients based on their skills, certifications, and location. This platform has been developed in parallel with the mAKE project, led by the Internet of Production and supported by the RISA Fund and the UK government during the new Innovative Manufacturing in Africa 2024, sister project of the mAKE project.

Figure 8: Maker Passport platform for makers to create their profiles and share their skills

Throughout the project runtime, the PSS and the maker passport research was shared with the community through multiple channels:

- Presentation of the maker passport to participants of the Maker in Residency Programme and collection of feedback
- Global events: Leaflets were produced to present the maker passport and the other technical innovations developed during the mAKE project. These flyers were shared during international events such as AfriLabs and Vulca Seminar in November 2024 together with presentations and workshops organised to discuss the concepts.
- Community calls were organised with REFFAO and AOSH
- A mAKE Talk was recorded to present the maker passport

Figure 9: WP4 Technical Innovations leaflet

Outcomes:

Interviews conducted with makerspaces leaders, who participated in the IMA project and in our research development on the authentication-based digital maker passport, shared feedback on the use of Maker Passports. The concept of the Maker Passport offers several insightful lessons that can be applied to community building, international collaboration and skills development:

1. Empowering communities through skill mapping

The Maker Passport connects skilled individuals globally, enabling collaboration on replicable projects that address local and humanitarian challenges. By formalising processes and mapping talents, it enhances efficiency in solving crises and organizing events like makerthons.

2. Enhancing capacity and collaboration

Access to a database of makers allows for targeted outreach and capacity building. It fosters knowledge-sharing, collaborative problem-solving, and community empowerment by leveraging and transferring universal skills across borders.

3. Driving impact through formalized processes

The Maker Passport simplifies the process of identifying and organizing skills, ensuring efficiency, flexibility, and scalability. It underscores the value of clear, structured systems in maximizing the impact of makerspaces and benefiting their communities.

A table that provides a summary of main outputs and outcomes related to the maker passport can be found in [Annex 1](#).

Lessons learnt:

The strong involvement of the community in the development and testing of the maker passport concept strongly enriched the process of the prototype creation and helped to create processes that can be supported and maintained by the makerspace ecosystem. It was an important and initial step in stimulating awareness for the topic of sharing certified skills in the community. Discussions with REFFAO and AOSH will be continued to foster a wider uptake of the maker passport system. This work is very much connected to the work on the distributed contracting system, explained below.

6.2 Map of Machinery

Output:

The Map of Machinery is a Geographic Information System (GIS) developed to locate, analyse, and enhance the accessibility of small-scale manufacturing capabilities. As part of a broader Distributed Manufacturing Network, it serves as a bridge between makers, communities, and stakeholders across Africa and Europe. As the map was already developed the focus of the Y3 was on the usability of such a tool.

Through a series of documented interviews and working group meetings, a selection of attributes and motivations for data collection and mapping was synthesized into four primary use cases: 1) Finding Manufacturing Sites for Open-Source Projects, 2) Employment Creation Guidelines, 3) Maker-Space Learning and Setup Guidelines, and 4) Rapid Response Procurement Tool.

Case 4, Rapid Response Procurement, was selected for tool development with the mission to encourage data collection and promote the purpose of data sharing between partner organisations. The project produced a data policy document, database specifications, analysis reports, and computer code for the retrieval, wrangling and validation of data, as well as a self-hosted AI model for natural-language processing.

A data privacy policy was developed for the Map of machinery to assure compliance with GDPR regulations: <https://map.internetofproduction.org/data-privacy-policy/index.html>.

In case of an emergency response, spaces that have their location masked for privacy reasons will be temporarily given open access to geolocation information. A protocol has been drafted to quickly respond to an emergency situation.

New portable maps were developed for online and offline use. With a new design and new customised functions (near me search, search bar, ruler, fullscreen option and notification panel, the maps offer better performance and include data protection layers. <https://map.internetofproduction.org/makeafricaeu.html>

A new submission form was created and shared with the mAKE networks to continue to populate the map. The form is hosted on KoboToolBox that offers the offline-collection mode.

<https://map.internetofproduction.org/data-submission/index.html>

KoboToolbox has proven to be an effective tool for collecting device and location metadata, enabling efficient data filtering. Kobo gives the best data validation robustness, its open-source licensing and free hosting by UNHCR made it the best suitable tool for the purpose for the Map of Machinery.

At the end of the mAKE project an overall count of **20,000 records** was aggregated, and after filtering out were obtained **10,308 unique records** with a minimal set of attributes “name, (latitude, longitude, or address), (capability or machine), and (URL, e-mail or phone number)”.

Outcomes:

The work on the map of machinery created strong interest in the European and African ecosystem of makerspaces and DIHs. The many data points which were added to the map throughout the project run time, help finding manufacturing sites for open-source projects, thus they have the potential to stimulate local economic growth with new business opportunities and job creation.

As one of the involved makerspace representatives states: “With the map of the machinery, we are able to know the machines found in different makerspaces - making it easy to work together on different projects and meet tight deadlines. Even share learnings from machine operations and project executions.” Thus it makes local production more efficient and collaborative.

In case of a potential future emergency, comparable to what the world experienced in 2020 during the COVID-19 crisis, the map also helps localising and accessing critical supplies for a quick response.

A table that provides a summary of main outputs and outcomes related to the Map of Machinery can be found in [Annex 1](#).

Lessons learnt:

1. **Sustained Engagement is Key:** Short-term involvement leads to incomplete datasets and interrupted workflows. Continuous engagement strategies, like consistent communication and clear incentives, are necessary to keep participants motivated.
2. **Prioritize Data Quality Early:** Addressing data quality issues during collection is far more effective than fixing problems later. Early implementation of validation checks and quality controls is vital.

3. **Trust is Fundamental to Data Sharing:** Privacy concerns must be addressed with solutions like GDPR compliance and privacy-focused data designs tailored to specific communities. Enhancing digital literacy also promotes responsible data sharing.
4. **Balance Incentives with Quality:** Financial incentives can motivate data sharing but may lead to issues like duplicate or low-quality entries. Designing incentive mechanisms that align with data integrity is crucial.
5. **Building Effective Frameworks Takes Effort:** Developing transparent and maintainable systems is resource-intensive. Success depends on active community involvement and challenging existing norms to drive innovation within set timelines.

6.3 Digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing

WP4's prototype digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing aims to enable contracting of decentralised work to several DIHs/makerspaces, such that the DIHs/makerspaces can be contracted to perform manufacturing functions for a single purchase order. The contracting prototype aims, among other things, to enable (through building in quality assurance steps) contractor trust in a process through which a contract is fulfilled by several small-scale manufacturers in diverse locations rather than by a single, larger manufacturer.

Distributed manufacturing represents a shift from centralised production to localised, smaller scale manufacturing networks, enabling products to be designed, produced, and distributed closer to end-users. While this approach offers flexibility, cost reduction, and local empowerment, it also introduces significant complexities in contracting due to decentralised roles and varying stakeholder responsibilities.

Outputs:

A digital contracting system, based on one specific model, has been developed to a framework for contracting for distributed manufacturing scenarios. The system simulates order placement and completion to ensure transparency, accountability and efficiency in distributed workflows. Virtual trials were conducted to test the prototype system for one chosen distributed manufacturing scenario.

Such a system, with clear role assignments, enables a smoother collaboration among distributed manufacturing stakeholders. It improves production processes, streamlining DM workflows with automation and quality assurance mechanisms leading to more efficient and consistent production outputs.

Figure 10: Digital Contracting prototype platform to distribute orders for distributed manufacturing

The contracting for distributed manufacturing was tested by 27 makers with a model contract in 2023. Since October 2024, approx. 62 people have tested the digital contracting system based on the learning of previous research and the distributed manufacturing trials.

Outcomes:

The testing of the distributed manufacturing that was organised throughout the IMA project and in workshop settings in the A-MEG (African Makerspace Ecosystem Gathering) 2024 and Vulca Seminar 2024 stimulated first highly interesting and relevant discussions about this new approach of local, distributed manufacturing.

The feedback of test participants showed that it has the potential for democratizing and boosting local production, reducing costs, and lowering environmental impact, particularly in underserved regions. But in the discussions with a broad variety of makerspace and DIH representatives important challenges were identified, like quality assurance, role clarity and legal considerations, as areas requiring further exploration for scalability.

The participation in the distributed manufacturing trial was an interesting learning experience for participants as the following community voices from two involved makerspaces (one in Ghana and one in Kenya) show.

Community Voices about the distributed manufacturing trial:

MAKE African European Maker
Innovation Ecosystem

Distributed manufacturing – makers get ready to participate in production!

Supporting localised and distributed manufacturing via new technologies enables makerspaces to fill critical gaps in local markets on a commercial basis. Shorter supply chains and lower shipping costs can make local manufacturing competitive and bring business opportunities for makers, makerspaces and their local manufacturing networks. With this vision the mAKE project worked on innovative distributed manufacturing infrastructures that support sharing skills, machinery and contracts thus facilitating the contracting process with many manufacturers .

Distributed manufacturing trials with two makerspaces

To test the innovative infrastructures developed in mAKE and collect feedback on its usefulness and applicability, **two makerspaces from Ghana and Kenya were involved in a trial** where they used the maker passport prototype, map of machinery and contracting model. As part of the trial, the makerspaces registered their machines on the map of machinery, individual makers signed up to the maker passport and were contracted to produce a series of distributed manufacturing items.

Both makerspaces saw this trial as an opportunity to attract new members eager to learn new skills. They took the initiative to organize 3D printing training sessions before the trial, preparing new members for their participation and encouraging individuals to engage and grow within the community. Here is the feedback from Michael and Derrick, two managers of makerspaces in Ghana and Kenya, from their participation in training and trials:

Michael, Triple Dimension, Ghana

Metal fabricators are at the heart of Michael's makerspace's growing community. Traditionally working in their own spaces, these artisans began visiting the makerspace to tackle more complex, technology-driven tasks. For many, the trials and associated training introduced them to tools like laser cutting and 3D printing—technologies that opened up new creative possibilities and fostered opportunities for collaboration.

The trials, which were conducted in 2023, were a significant success. Triple Dimension's setup of diverse machines across multiple locations allowed makers to explore advanced techniques and solutions. The experience led to a major milestone: securing their own

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MAKE African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem

rented space, which not only offered a dedicated workshop but also enabled Triple Dimension to expand their impact by teaching in Kumasi.

The response from participating makers was overwhelmingly positive. Many expressed a strong interest in engaging in future projects, eager to continue learning and leveraging the makerspace's resources. A key insight from the trials was the collaborative spirit among makers. The process of generating costs proved straightforward, with artisans working together to develop estimates and share ideas—a testament to the community's growing synergy.

Building on this momentum, Triple Dimension recently took a major step by registering an association of metal workers. This initiative aims to deepen collaboration within the

metalworking community. They are now engaging in discussions on how to leverage their collective skills and resources for future projects, further strengthening the network of makers. By introducing cutting-edge tools, fostering collaboration, and creating a space for growth, Triple Dimension is empowering metal fabricators to innovate, learn, and expand their creative horizons.

Picture: Metal worker, Kisumu, Ghana – photo credit: Triple Dimension (2023)

Derrick, IOME 254, Kenya

The trial provided a unique opportunity for makers and innovators of [I.O.Me 254](#) to harness their skills and resources in a meaningful way. Designed to engage youth, the trials emphasized how hands-on training can be monetized by distributed manufacturing, motivating participants to see a direct and tangible outcome from their efforts. By equipping young people with practical skills, the program offered a promising alternative to quicker but less sustainable jobs, like motorcycle work. Recognizing the challenges of maintaining youth engagement, the program focused on quick skill acquisition and visible results to keep participants motivated and focused.

A significant highlight of the initiative was its contribution to special needs education. Writing aids were produced in the trials and donated to special needs schools, marking the beginning of a long-term partnership aimed at creating useful tools for pupils. The team was also invited to a Rotary Club event supporting children with cerebral deficiencies.

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101016858

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016858.

MAKE African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem

Faced with the need to produce more writing aids quickly, they efficiently scaled production and successfully delivered the tools.

The writing aid has become a signature product that the makers are committed to improving. By actively seeking user feedback, they aim to enhance the design and functionality to better meet the needs of students and teachers. The trials not only empowered youth with practical skills and entrepreneurial opportunities but also fostered social impact by addressing the needs of vulnerable communities. Through collaboration, innovation, and a focus on quality, the initiative continues to create positive change, inspiring young makers to build a sustainable and impactful future.

Picture: Girl manipulating a 3D printer, Lamu, Kenya – Photo credit IOME254 (2023)

Quote from Derrick on the Maker Passport: "The sign up form was easy to fill. Being able to map out makers with various skills is very useful at times when one is looking for specific skills within a certain location. And IOMe being makerspace in humanitarian context the people and skills will be useful to identify and reach out to makers when in need of solving humanitarian challenges and emergencies. For instance, if we are looking to host a makerthone, we contact the right people since we can be able to access them."

For more information on the distributed manufacturing infrastructure, please access:

- <https://www.internetofproduction.org/innovative-manufacturing-in-africa>
- <https://community.internetofproduction.org/t/ima-distributed-manufacturing-trials/447/25>

This project has received funding from the European Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101016858

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016858.

A table that provides a summary of main outputs and outcomes related to the digital contracting system can be found in [Annex 1](#).

Lessons learnt:

From the Distributed Manufacturing virtual trials, participants shared their feedback on the prototype system tested and how valuable this can be in distributed manufacturing scenarios.

The questions asked right after the trials were:

1. Could this system motivate you to engage in distributed manufacturing? If yes, what is the main value?
2. How can automation of contracting make your production process more efficient? If so, would it be for the whole process or a particular part? And why?
3. How would you envision a distributed manufacturing contracting system to be? What should it include and how easy should it be to initiate?

Their feedback highlights the importance of designing adaptable, transparent, and user-focused distributed manufacturing systems while addressing the inherent challenges of decentralization and fostering collaboration across diverse stakeholders. Key lessons learned from the participants' feedback:

1. Quality Control and Automation:

- Centralized, makerspace-managed, or self-inspection methods were explored for consistent quality assurance, with pre-production inspections suggested to avoid disruptions.
- Automation, clear briefs, and workflows enhance transparency, efficiency, and standardization, though makerspace capacity limits remain a challenge.

2. Collaboration and Trust:

- Trust between stakeholders can be supported by certification, training, or adding smaller organizations. Balancing open-source innovation with financial sustainability is essential for effective collaboration.

3. Makerspaces and Logistics:

- Makerspaces serve as hubs for creativity, education, and local logistics, not just production. Collective purchasing and centralized logistics help address material sourcing and currency differences.

4. User-Centered and Scalable Design:

- Aligning production with user needs ensures relevance, while training and governance frameworks (e.g., certifications) address scalability challenges.

7. Communication, dissemination and outreach (WP5)

WP5 is dedicated to the communication and dissemination of project outputs and findings to defined target audiences in the best communicable form. The aim of the outreach activities is to maximise project impact and support the project’s capacity building, community engagement and network-building, providing key stakeholders with the necessary information in a time-effective manner that allows for early engagement, market uptake, and implementation. The communication and dissemination work of the mAKE project has, as of January 2024 (last month of Y2), generated the following outputs and initial outcomes:

Table 2: Communication and dissemination KPIs

WP5 activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Develop and establish a dissemination and outreach campaign</p> <p>Create project identity, website and social media</p> <p>Define and develop guidelines for capacity building tools for social innovation</p> <p>Set of recommendations for global innovation ecosystem technical solution for platform integration</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliverable D5.1: Communication, Dissemination and Outreach (CDO) Plan (M3) • Clear and recognisable visual identity (M3) • Deliverable D5.4: Guidelines, templates and how-tos for best practices for designing project outputs and self-learning tools (M12) • Deliverable D5.3: Recommendations for technical solutions of platform integration (M36) <p>Website</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 35.477 total page views (including partner’s website) <p>Online/offline events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 133 events in which mAKE participated • 94.078 participants in mAKE-related events <p>Social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 127.622 views across all social media channels • 622 posts on social media • 1.957 followers across all social media (567 on Instagram, 272 on Twitter, 104 on Facebook, 947 on LinkedIn) • 43 videos shared on YouTube <p>Newsletter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2.621 subscribers • 13 newsletters sent by mAKE • 20 newsletters by mAKE partners <p>Final outcomes:</p>

WP5 activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increase in engagement and reach through the webinar series of the OCBM (9 live webinars), in which the maker ecosystem could actively participate, exchange knowledge and networking ● Continuous cooperation on event promotion between WP5 and WP6, and between these two WPs and WPs 1-4, has generated increasingly strong website and social media statistics ● Awareness of mAKE among the project's stakeholder groups has continued to grow through the project's use of social media and the project's participation in numerous events ● Mutual learning and experience-sharing, between the mAKE consortium and the project's stakeholders, has been facilitated through the implementation of two series of talks, the "Knowledge Pills" (9 videos) and the "mAKE talks" (7 videos) ● Increased visibility and acknowledgment to the authors of deliverables and resources on mAKE resource page

Lessons learnt

As concerning communication, we can underline:

- The growth of the mAKE community has been significantly bolstered by participation in strategic local and international events across Africa and Europe.
- The combination of online and offline communication strategies has proven highly effective in disseminating information and fostering connections within the maker ecosystem. This has been further supported by the availability of open resources, which continue to enhance the ecosystem and its environment.
- The MiR residencies have played a crucial role in connecting African and European makerspaces, serving as a key element in the communication and dissemination of mAKE's activities.
- We have received overwhelmingly positive feedback regarding the design and visual identity of the mAKE project. This includes both digital and physical communication materials, which have been well-received for their professionalism and appeal. Notably, this design legacy will continue through its adoption by the new makerspace entity, ensuring its impact endures beyond the project's lifespan.
- Monthly online meetings have maintained a strong focus on communication and dissemination, encouraging partners to actively contribute to ongoing initiatives, such as the publication of the mAKE Talk series.
- The creation of communication guidelines, including resources such as webinar guidelines, has been instrumental in effectively engaging partners and ensuring the success of collaborative initiatives.

8. Community engagement and sustainability (WP6)

Outputs:

WP6, led in the mAKE consortium by GIG, was dedicated to active community engagement, ensuring that the mAKE stakeholder communities were involved in the co-creation of mAKE outputs. The WP aimed to meet the real needs of target communities and support bottom-up development of sustainable knowledge and infrastructure. The activities of WP6 linked closely to WP5's dissemination and communication work, and to all the content creation and digital infrastructure development in WPs 1 to 4. The key engaged actors of this work package were the makers, technology developers, startups, SMEs, DIHs/makerspaces and leaders of DIHs/makerspaces, many of whom were part of the mAKE consortium members' networks. These actors have all been actively engaged in the co-development of mAKE outputs and outcomes.

WP6 completed the co-creation report with the consortium partner group totaling 204 co-creation sessions. 133 online and offline events took place across at least 13 African and six European countries with the addition of the UK, Scotland, and global inputs from specifically events in Mexico and the USA during the course of the project. A total of 94,078 community members have been engaged over the project term.

WP6 worked closely with WP2 and WP4 lead consortium entities, the AMN and IOPA, on hosting the inaugural AMEG (Africa Makerspace Ecosystem Gathering) in Cape Town, South Africa near the end of Y3 (November 2024). This AMEG featured several mAKE workshops and panel discussions, including sessions focused on fostering deeper connections between AU and EU DIH/makerspace community members in attendance toward sustaining mAKE.

In support of WP1's Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM), in Y3 WP6 continued to co-host the final three WP6-WP1 community discussion webinars, with a focus on community inputs for, awareness of, and engagement with, the OCBM. Also as part of the consortium's knowledge creation and sharing, five 'mAKE Talks' were prepared featuring the Venture Building Handbook by GT, the MOOC by APSOHA, Policy Recommendations for Makerspaces by AMN, the AfricaOSH Summit by AOSH and the Map of Machinery by IOPA. The recordings of these webinars have been disseminated through consortium members' networks and embedded into the dedicated mAKE YouTube channel linked to the mAKE website. In 2024, seven 'mAKE Talks' were produced which provide insights into the project resources and community, which are embedded in the website.

WP6 collaborated with WP1 (and WP5 on communication materials) for the Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme (see Chapter 3 on WP1) which officially took place from June 2024 for four African makers (two male, two female) in four European Makerspaces, the one month on-site residency and the following reporting continued for the period until November 2024. Additionally, a hybrid residency took place in

November 2024 alongside a dedicated makerspace track and panel at the Afrilabs Gathering and a curated conference at the A-MEG.

GIG hosted a further 8 online community calls, three of which focused on the MIR programme, as well as two in-person presentations of the programme at the Vulca Annual Seminars in 2023 (Slovenia) and 2024 (Germany) and presenting the Makers in a community meetup at re:publica in June 2024 (Germany). More than 410 community members engaged through the total of 13 WP6 dedicated community calls and/or webinars during 2024. 30 new individuals and 15 makerspaces/organisations have joined the GIG community on-boarded into GIG's communication channels, gaining access to numerous opportunities and valuable resources. This integration allows them to connect with counterparts worldwide, fostering an exchange of best practices within the ecosystem.

Sharing and Embedding:

The Learning Hub of Distributed Design Platform³ serves as a hosting platform for the mAKE MOOC, within WP3. Through this platform, over one hundred resources of ten thematic areas and navigate it through filters. The mAKE MOOC courses and resources that have been produced have been added to the Learning Hub and are available and organized into thematic areas according to their focus. Additionally, building on the central goal of the mAKE project to create a shared understanding of the explicit, implicit, tacit, and procedural knowledge necessary for individual makers to participate in and easily navigate a distributed manufacturing ecosystem. Additionally, 19 resources have, to date, been embedded in the online assets of the mAKE project and its consortium members.

Sustainability:

The consortium participated in physical and online co-creation sessions to explore, document, and enhance the project's sustainability after funding concludes. Notably, several initiatives have already become synonymous with the continuation and legacy of mAKE. Funding has been allocated for makerspaces in Africa through consortium member IOPA and the RISA Foundation in 2024, which has helped connect and promote makerspaces on the continent through e.g. the inaugural [Makerspace Track](#) as part of the Afrilabs Annual Summit, recording the highest attendance at the gathering with over one hundred and five participants in the sessions. Consequently, sustainability in action showcased essential activities that enhance the project's impact and pave the way for future projects, funding, and additional initiatives.

- IOPA secured matching funding to support the OCBM from the **Innovative Manufacturing in Africa (IMA) project**. This funding facilitated the development of a dedicated website⁴, and its translation

³ <https://learn.distributeddesign.eu>

⁴ <https://localeconomies.org/blueprints>

into French in late 2023. The IMA⁵ is funded by the UK International Development's Research and Innovation Systems for Africa (RISA) Fund⁶,

- In late 2023, Anna Lowe from Manufacturing Change Ltd. (WP1), the developer of the OCBM, established a **mentoring program** for makerspaces to enhance their use of the catalog. There were thirty five applications from makerspaces for just three mentoring opportunities highlighting the demand. The selected mentee spaces include Garoua in Cameroon, iZone Hub in Zimbabwe, and Habitat Augsburg in Germany.
 - In 2024, the **IMA project** received an additional grant, enabling ongoing collaboration between IMA and mAKE on the OCBM. As part of this new grant, the mentoring program will be expanded, allowing makerspaces from four additional IMA countries (Ghana, Nigeria, Kenya, and South Africa) to apply for mentoring support.
- A new EU proposal was approved for the **Make-a-thek** initiative. Drawing inspiration from the collaborative ethos and innovative objectives of the **mAKE Project**, this initiative stands out as a further follow-up sustainability activity. It serves as a tangible outcome of the project while bringing a unique approach connecting a well-integrated ecosystem of libraries, craftworkers and maker spaces, open-source hardware innovation, and community-driven initiatives to deliver sustainable, scalable solutions that address pressing global challenges.

In 2025, a **mAKE secretariat** will be established in Cape Town, South Africa, where the final consortium meeting for 2024 took place. By enhancing our collaborations with the African network – Rlabs⁷, based in Cape Town – we aim to cultivate a supportive local environment that facilitates the effective management of ongoing marketing and promotional activities aligned with the project's objectives and outcomes.

Lessons learnt

A critical learning stems from the continuous visa issues experienced throughout the project term, especially pertaining to the MIR programme which resulted in delays toward execution. The initial programme was able to host 4 African makers in 4 European makerspaces with an additional 5th African maker hosted in a hybrid model since he was unable to gain a visa. Some of the issues cited was power outages at the embassy forcing extended closures, long travel times from the makers village to the main city where the embassy is located where appointments were missed due to transport delays, among others. Issues were collected via a survey from the consortium and summarized in policy brief by GIG.

⁵ <https://www.internetofproduction.org/innovative-manufacturing-awards>.

⁶ <https://www.risa-fund.org/>

⁷ <https://rlabs.org/>

9. Summary & Conclusions: Overall KPIs and lessons learned at the end of Y3

When the mAKE consortium met for the first time in early 2022, we defined a clear vision of what we want to achieve by the end of the three project years. This vision can be seen at the right-hand side of the following picture and was the baseline for the evaluation and impact assessment activities in this project.

Figure 11: Expectations and project vision defined at the project Kick-Off in early 2022

We have **co-created and iteratively shaped an important number of resources, products and methods** to support makerspaces and DIHs in running their businesses more sustainably and successfully. The strong engagement of the makerspace eco-system in the co-creation process helped us to elicit the needs and requirements of the involved stakeholders and iteratively shape the mAKE outputs accordingly. The co-creation work showed that innovators and managers of makerspaces and DIHs are strongly focused on making and innovating, which fits perfectly well with their backgrounds, and generates important impacts in their local communities. But hardly have they encountered the occasions to think about how to sustain their businesses, how to make a successful product out of an innovation or how to attract investors to their

activities. Nor have they had the time and budget to do advocacy work towards policy makers at local, regional and international scale. mAKE resources like the Open Catalogue of Business Models, the Venture Building handbook and programme, or the Policy recommendations have successfully closed this gap. The collected questionnaires and interviews show how much impact we had in raising awareness and knowledge in makerspaces about these new topics and providing resources that are easy to understand and well adaptable and applicable to the very different contexts of makerspaces in Africa and Europe. This resulted in new business models that were successfully implemented, in venture capital that was successfully acquired, in sustainable relationships with other founders, investors or policy makers that were established.

With the work on the technical infrastructure – the maker passport, the map of machinery and the distributed contracting system – the mAKE project has not only developed technology to be used by makerspaces to ease the path towards distributed, local manufacturing. We have also started the important dialog on how to document makers' skills and competencies across different continents and how to proceed with the very complex issue of distributed productions. The result of these discussions fed the iterative development of the technical mAKE infrastructure, but most importantly attracted major players to continue the work on distributed manufacturing (e.g. ReFFAO –Réseau Francophone des FabLab d'Afrique de l'Ouest).

mAKE supported the makerspace ecosystem in Africa and Europe with an impressive number of events that helped to create **fruitful and sustaining relationships between makers, makerspace managers, founders, innovators, investors, policymakers and educators**. The feedback of participants shows that these encounters, trainings, discussions, and matchmaking activities had a huge impact on individual makers, makerspaces and their communities. Our work showed that mAKE activities had more visibility and impact in Africa as in Europe – as European makerspaces are already better supported in their ecosystems. The strong engagement of mAKE in Africa, the building of fruitful collaborations between European and African makers, strongly impacted the establishment of an makerspace community in Africa and influenced their self-understanding in which potential directions they could grow – e.g. becoming local manufacturers or establishing links to policy makers. The A-MEG (African Makerspace Ecosystem Gathering) organised in Cape Town in November 2024 as final event of the mAKE project attracted over 70 makers from Africa and Europe, attaining sessions focused on fostering deeper connections between African and European DIH/makerspace community members toward sustaining mAKE. Also the makerspace track at the Afrilabs Gathering in November 2024 demonstrates the strong self-perception of makerspaces as being important innovation centres on the African continent. From European makerspaces we heard that they perceive it as a highly important and impactful contribution of mAKE, that makerspaces are officially seen as digital innovation hubs now. Which results in 63 African makerspaces being listed on the DIHIWARE platform as digital innovation hubs (<https://eurescom-lfr.6g-ia.eu/group/guest/african-dihs>).

All the mAKE resources are provided as open source documents on the mAKE website, the Zenodo platform, the communication platforms of the mAKE consortium partners and most importantly the mAKE MOOC, where additional training material guides people in using the mAKE resources.

During the runtime of the project, we have started successful talks with follow-up projects, like LAUDS (<https://lauds.eu/>), to take over the MOOC content. The **A-MEG (African Makerspace Ecosystem Gathering)** inaugurated as a new makerspace network organisation at the end of 2024 and commits to continue working with the mAKE resources. In addition, mAKE consortium partners have kicked-off the mAKE secretariat, which is presented in our Sustainability plan (D6.4) and will continue the work which was so successfully started during the project runtime.

Throughout the project we experienced the **power of co-creation** which has been key to understanding the complex processes and entities involved in creating automated processes that successfully address challenges such as linking to existing inventory lists, avoiding data duplication, ensuring data currency, simplifying upload processes, and maintaining data quality.

We were frequently reminded of the **importance of person-to-person interactions**, especially when trustful relationships for cross-continental collaboration, innovation and business creation should be established.

But also, for the work with policy makers we realised how important encounters of political decision makers and makerspace representatives during conferences and meetings are. These are occasions to get a common understanding on requirements and expectations, paving the way for governmental partnerships and collaboration on national projects, providing makerspaces with opportunities to contribute their expertise and resources toward addressing societal challenges, while also raising their profile and influence. Face-to-face investor trips to makerspaces allows delegations to engage more deeply with makers, innovators and their ecosystem, thus significantly enhancing connections and support. Also targeted investor matching and fundraising, including both in-person and digital pitch events, turned out to be very important.

The visa-problems that African makers encountered when they wanted to visit mAKE events are a strong limiting factor for all these fruitful, in-person interactions to happen.

Personal interactions help to create **trust**, which is of great importance if DIHs/makerspaces and makers from Africa and Europe are to be able to successfully collaborate and learn from each other and then also reach out to other stakeholder groups based on successful collaborations. An example from the mAKE project, is that the makerspace association Vulca has emerged as an important trusted interface between the mAKE consortium and European makers. In WP4's testing of digital contracting for distributed manufacturing, trust—in the skills of makers, in the quality of created products, in the reliability of involved producers and purchasers—has been identified as an important requirement. This can be fostered by previous relationships and working experiences, in the long run the developed infrastructures (for WP4's

digital contract prototype for distributed manufacturing, and for other mAKE deliverables) should also support the generation of trust.

Makerspace network organizations can play a huge role in creating awareness for the impact of makerspaces/DIHs in both Europe and Africa amongst important stakeholders like policy makers, founders and investors, while at the same time supporting their members with continuous training and occasions to meet, share and learn from each other.

For all this work future funding is an important issue to continue the work of mAKE and further deepen connections between Africa and European DIHs/makerspaces.

Table 3: Project outputs, outcomes and impacts

	Micro level (individual makers, innovators, etc.)	Meso level (makerspaces, DIHs, startups, etc.)	Macro level (associations, networks, policy level, etc.)
Key outputs	<p>Individual participants actively involved in co-designing, shaping and using the mAKE outputs</p> <p>Makers-in-Residency (MiR) programme:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MiR 1.0: 66 makers applied, 4 selected • MiR 2.0: 45 makers applied, 16 shortlisted, 4 selected and hosted by European makerspaces • MiR 3.0: 1 hybrid MiR <p>Open Makerspace Toolkit, Training-of-Trainers and MOOC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approximately 80 existing OERs and 3 OERs created by the mAKE consortium included in the Toolkit, published as an adaptable, open access web platform • Open Makerspace Toolkit accessed online by 1312 visitors (Nov 2023 to Jan 2025); downloaded 185 times from the mAKE website (Oct 	<p>DIHs/makerspaces, startups and SMEs and other relevant stakeholders actively involved in co-designing, shaping and using the mAKE outputs</p> <p>Venture building programme and handbook:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 companies selected for Venture Building programme (out of 53 who applied) • 20 individual needs assessment sessions conducted • 130 hours of Venture Building provided • 3 pitch training workshops • Start-up Trip to Cairo with 8 startups organised • 1 Venture Building Handbook in English and French version created and downloaded 420 times (only between Oct 2024 and Jan 2025) • 21 makerspace representatives attending the Venture Building Training-of-Trainer (ToT) • 6 interactive workshops conducted during the ToT 	<p>Political decision-makers and representatives of DIH associations involved in co-designing, shaping, using the mAKE outputs</p> <p>mAKE events to create and discuss policy agenda and recommendations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 69 participants in 11 focus group discussions and 7 interviews • 26 participants to the community discussion webinar on common policy agenda • 11 events attended by mAKE to share the Common Policy Agenda: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 in Africa • 4 in Europe • 2 virtual events • 400 participation from stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 42 policy makers • over 100 makers

	<p>2024 to Jan 2025)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Planning and organising of 5 training-of-trainers events in Barcelona, Yaoundé, Abidjan, Berlin and Accra with overall 74 participants ● MOOC launched with 2 webinars and approx. 100 participants ● 86 people registered for the MOOC after the 2 webinars <p>mAKE events and social media:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 133 events in which mAKE participated ● 94.078 participants in mAKE-related events ● 35.477 total page views (including partner’s website) ● 127.622 views across all social media channels ● 622 posts on social media ● 1.957 followers across all social media ● 43 videos shared on YouTube ● 2.621 subscribers ● 13 newsletters sent by mAKE ● 20 newsletters by mAKE partners <p>mAKE infrastructure developed and tested:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 96 responses to the survey that collected requirements for the PSS/Maker Passport system ● Prototype of PSS/Maker Passport system developed (M18) ● 45 makers sign up for the PSS/Maker Passport ● Testing of a distributed production system by 27 makers in 2023 and 62 makers in 2024. 	<p>mAKE Open Business Model Catalogue created, tested and shared:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Over 100 participants in 6 workshops to co-create the OBMC ● 50 successful DIHs/makerspaces interviewed for development of OCBM ● 17 published business models ● 8 webinars linked to OCBM with over 200 participants ● 3 makerspaces (in Germany, Cameroon, Zimbabwe) involved in a mentoring programme using the OCBM ● 7 makerspaces in Africa involved in a mentoring program using the OCBM ● OCBM successfully implemented by at least 10 makerspaces <p>mAKE networking events organised:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 28 founder-to-founder (F2F) matchmaking events ● 2 business-to-business (B2B) networking event <p>mAKE digital Infrastructure developed and tested:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 9 makerspaces (in Ghana, Kenya and South Africa) tested PSS/Maker Passport prototype, Map of Machinery and the digital contracting system for distributed manufacturing ● 20,000 records and 10,308 unique entries in the Map of Machinery: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● over 250 participants from the private sector <p>mAKE resources created and shared:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 7 case studies of collective organisation and policy-related actions by DIH/makerspace associations created and shared ● Common Policy Agenda and Recommendations for Policy Makers completed and downloaded 368 times only between Oct. and Jan. 2024 ● Sharing of approx. 100 printed policy brief ● Over 850 social media reach
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<p>Intermediate outcomes</p>	<p>Capacity building and knowledge gains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Powerful mutual-experience exchange, co-creation, awareness-raising, and learning at individual level amongst the engaged makers • Greatly improved engagement with European makers and makerspaces through collaboration with Vulca network • Increased knowledge amongst the key audiences on how to set up, manage and equip DIHs and makerspaces (based on OERs and MOOC) • Mutual learning between involved makers and makerspaces of the makers-in-residency programme <p>Co-creation of mAKE infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved upload processes for the PSS/Maker Passport system • Better understanding of processes and requirements for digital contracting system • Identified challenges of distributed manufacturing, e.g. quality assurance and role clarity <p>Increased collaboration between makers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through all the mAKE events and community building • Through the different mentoring and ToT programmes, the F2F and B2B events • Through the new relationships created in the mAKE project 	<p>Capacity building and knowledge gains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Powerful mutual-experience exchange, co-creation, awareness-raising, and learning at a makerspace level • Increased practical knowledge about different successful business models for startups and makerspaces • Increased knowledge and understanding on Venture Building and options running makerspaces more sustainably • Increased knowledge and awareness about distributed manufacturing • Exploration of innovative funding mechanisms for makerspaces <p>Practical steps towards higher sustainability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher financial sustainability through new business models successfully applied by local businesses • SMEs/startups in the Venture Building programme able to make it to the next stage of venture building • 60,000 Euro secured funding and 3 million Euro pending funding opportunities from the Venture Building programme • Participants from the Venture Building ToT start to implement their new knowledge in their organizations - trying out new business opportunities and consulting their members • Participants from the Makerspace Toolkit ToT provide support to other makerspaces in setting up and running makerspaces <p>Co-creation of mAKE infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback from makerspaces led to redesign of the inventory form for the Map of Machinery • Identification of important aspects in distributed manufacturing, e.g. quality 	<p>Capacity building and knowledge gains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-depth mutual-experience exchange, co-creation, awareness-raising, and learning about policy requirements and recommendations of makerspaces/DIHs • Increased knowledge on how to support DIHs in the different national contexts • Increased understanding of how to develop and trigger bottom-up DIH networks <p>Strengthened relationships:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthened relationships between policy makers and makers through dialogue and <p>Commitment and awareness amongst policy makers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Close collaboration with local decision-makers and local institutions in policy formulation • Enhanced awareness about the impact of makerspaces amongst policy makers • Increased commitment of government officials to support the agenda <p>Inclusion of more African members in DIH/makerspace networks</p>
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	<p>Strong community building in the African makerspace community and relationship building between European and African makerspaces</p>	<p>control, the diversity of roles required in such a system, the centrality of trust</p> <p>Increased collaboration and mutual learning between makers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable relationships have been created between makerspaces, innovators, founders, investors and policy makers <p>Visibility gains and increased collaboration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased transparency and improved demonstration of Machinery available <p>Facilitated finding of manufacturing sites for open-source projects and more efficient and collaborative local production</p>	
<p>Long-term outcomes (after Y3)</p>	<p>A sustainable repository of open-source methods, devices and products used and implemented by members of DIHs/makerspaces</p> <p>Increasing number of innovators</p> <p>Increasing number of co-created digital innovations</p>	<p>Opening business opportunities for African and European DIHs/makerspaces</p> <p>Increased revenue options for DIHs/makerspaces</p> <p>Sustainable usage of mAKE outputs</p> <p>New business alliances and more successful hardware startups and DIHs/makerspaces</p> <p>Scaling and replication of local production</p> <p>Raising uptake of distributed production</p>	<p>Changes in policies to support national and regional startup ecosystems</p> <p>Higher acceptance of DIHs/makerspaces by public authorities</p> <p>Better interfaces between the ecosystem players, including policy makers, DIHs/makerspaces, corporates and funders</p>

Annex 1

1. Tables of outputs and outcomes of mAkE main achievements:

Here are the detailed tables of each main achievement of the mAkE project.

Outputs are products or services resulting from the planned activities (e.g. workshops, participants in the workshops, etc.)
Outcomes are the effects of the outputs on the target group (e.g. a behaviour change, an increase in knowledge or skills, etc.)

1.1. OCBM

The OCBM activities, outputs and initial outcomes are summarised in the matrix below.

Table 4: Outputs and outcomes OCBM

WPI activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Document and disseminate an Open Catalogue of Business Models (OCBM)</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <p>D1.1: Open Catalogue of Business Models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 6 workshops held with over 100 participants in total, gathering information on how the OCBM could be most useful ● 50 individual interviews with successful DIHs/makerspaces representing a cross-section of sectors, geographic foci, and scales ● 17 published example business models for hardware DIHs/makerspaces and for ventures interaction with DIHs/makerspaces ● 8 webinars organised, with more than 200 participants in the webinars ● 3 Makerspaces mentored through a six-month program to learn skills to analyse and understand their market, use the OCBM to identify a suitable business model for test implementation, and go through an iterative process of testing and adapting the business model in their own context. 3 calls conducted with the full cohort, plus additional one-on-one calls between each makerspace and its mentor. ● A further 7 makerspaces in Africa have been through a mentoring program funded by RISA (see above) to make use of the OCBM. Positive feedback was also received from these makerspaces. <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Based on makerspace requirements “tags” were added to the online OCBM to allow for filtering by the context for which the model will be used ● Positive feedback from users of the catalogue: Makerspaces and those supporting makerspaces confirming that they are using the information and that it will be helpful to them ● The Ukrainian Maker Association has translated the OCBM into Ukrainian, https://makerua.org/business-models-for-makerspaces to share with its members; and mAkE is now in discussions with organisations who would like to translate the catalogue into French, Spanish and Portuguese, so as to share it with communities where English is not widely understood. ● Positive feedback was received from Makerspaces who have been through the mentoring program, saying they have been able to implement new business models and/or generate new revenue streams from their existing activities.. ● Based on learnings from the RISA mentoring program, training materials have been developed to help Makerspaces and hardware businesses develop skills that will aid them to use the OCBM more effectively. These will be published on the MOOC.

1.2. Venture Building programme

The activities, outputs and outcomes related to the Venture Building programme are summarised in the matrix below.

Table 5: Outputs and Outcomes Venture Building programme

WPI activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Set up and offer a company builder programme for ventures</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <p>Venture Building</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 53 companies (startups and SMEs) applied for the Venture Building and Business Development programme ● 3 GreenTec experts involved in shortlisting of 25 companies ● 1 kickoff call with Stakeholder Jury ● 20 companies selected for the programme ● 1 onboarding session with startups and experts convened ● 20 individual needs assessment sessions conducted ● 3 pitch training workshops ● 130+ out of 100 hours of Venture Building support were provided to companies ● Startup Trip to Cairo <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 8 startups joined (2 were also facing difficulties receiving their visa) ● 1 in-person pitch training ● 1 in-person pitch event and networking lunch in Cairo with 18 participants ● 1 Ecosystem Night with international investors and startups in Cairo ● 2 days participating in the Startup Without Borders Summit incl. 1:1 investor matchmaking and networking with international startups ● 1 Business-to-Business Matchmaking Event ● 1 community building trip to the Pyramids of Gizeh (self-paid) ● 1 additional online pitch event with 48 participants ● 1 baseline survey ● 1 feedback survey ● 1 pitch event feedback survey <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 20 company responses to the baseline survey component of the impact-tracking tool have demonstrated to us that networking opportunities and business growth are strong programme expectations among participating companies ● Both, business growth and networking have been tackled within the program through various measures: 1:1 Investor readiness support, 2 Pitch Events, Business-to-Business Networking Events, Ecosystem Night with international investors and startups in Cairo ● Funding received throughout the course of the VB program: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Secured= 60k€ plus ○ Pending Funding Opportunities= 3 Million €⁸ plus ● 8 company responses feedback survey Cairo Trip ● 8 company responses VB program feedback survey

⁸ Out of which one company has secured interest from a series of funds that are seeking matching equity investments, with over \$100 million available in these conditional funding opportunities. While this represents a significant potential for growth and investment, they are currently focused on securing a seed fund of \$3 million to kickstart their venture. This seed funding will provide the necessary foundation to leverage the larger matching funds, ensuring a strong financial base for future development and scaling. Another company is in the Due Diligence process for 197k €.

1.3. Venture Building Handbook and Training-of-Trainers

The activities, outputs and outcomes related to the Venture Building Handbook and the ToT are summarised in the matrix below.

Table 6: Outputs and outcomes Venture Building Handbook and ToTs

WPI activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Set up and offer a company builder programme for ventures</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <p>ToT:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 76 applications received after sharing with multiple European and African Networks and on social media channels (63= African makerspaces, 13= European makerspaces) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 25 experts confirmed attendance after selection process <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ European= 9 ■ African= 16 ● 6 interactive workshops held <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 on Business Models ○ 2 on Financial Analysis for Non-Financial Managers ○ 2 on Marketing and Distribution ● Course material such as homeworks, templates, workshop presentations as well as the recordings were shared with course participants ● 1 feedback survey <p>Venture Building Handbook (VBH) (M24)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● English and French version established ● Shared with program companies and makerspaces and on mAKE website & channels as well as GT social media ● MOOC Venture Building course based on the Venture Building Handbook ● 1 mAKE Talk introducing the VBH ● English version of the handbook downloaded 330 times only between Oct 20th, 2024 and Jan 30th, 2025 with numbers steadily increasing. The French version was downloaded 97 in the same period <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 10 makerspace experts were expected to be supported during the ToT. 14 successfully completed training in Venture Building and company support, earning program completion certificates. ● Additionally, seven experts were unable to attend the majority of sessions and, as a result, did not receive certificates. Since the material and recordings were shared, they had the opportunity to review the sessions at their convenience. ● Very positive feedback of participants related to a better understanding of venture building and how this knowledge has been or will be applied in their context.

1.4. Makers-in-Residency programme

The activities, outputs and outcomes related to the Makers-in-Residency are summarised in the matrix

Table 7: Outputs and outcomes MiRbelow.

WPI activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Organisation of the Makers-in-Residency Programme</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <p>Makers-in-Residency (MiR) 1.0</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 66 makers and 25 makerspaces applied for the MiR 1.0 programme ● 5 Stakeholder Jury members involved ● 6 makers and 5 makerspaces selected; 1 makerspace being available finally <p>MiR 2.0</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 46 makers and 4 makerspaces applied for the MiR 2.0 programme 16 makers were shortlisted for MiR 2.0 ● 6 makers and 4 makerspaces were chosen for residency ● 4 residency progress reports ● 4 residency feedback reports ● 4 blog posts ● 8 feedback interviews <p>MiR 3.0</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1 hybrid residency (European expert travelled to South Africa initially to collaborate on the prototype of a Cameroonian maker. Due to visa issues, the maker was not able to join in-person) ● 1 feedback interview ● Deliverable 1.3: Residency and Matchmaking Report <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Challenges encountered in delivery of MiR 1.0 led to recognition of need to reach out to a makerspace network (i.e., Vulca) with a strong European presence ● Collaboration with Vulca has greatly improved engagement with European makers and makerspaces (for MiR 2.0) ● Learnings were summarized and a manual on how to craft residencies has been shared publicly: The Art of Crafting Meaningful Residencies: Key Insights for Planners & Funders ● 104 maker applications for MiR in total ● 1 potential Afro-European company deriving from the funded Makers-in-Residency Program ● 5 prototypes advanced

1.4. Further matchmaking activities

Further matchmaking activities, outputs and outcomes are summarised in the matrix below.

Table 8: Outputs and outcomes further matchmaking

WP1 activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Offer targeted marketing and matchmaking services</p> <p>Organisation of: Founder-to-founder (F2F) matchmaking opportunities Business-to-Business (B2B) networking opportunities</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 28 Founder-to-Founder matchmaking events • 2 Business-to-Business networking events • Deliverable 1.3: Residency and Matchmaking Report <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several potential collaborations between businesses, projects, initiatives and investors initiated • Important lessons learned on establishing cross-continental relationships between SMEs, start-ups, founders and investors

1.4. Innovative funding mechanism

Activities, outputs and outcomes related to the definition of innovative funding mechanisms are summarised in the matrix below.

Table 9: Outputs and outcomes innovative funding

WP1 activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Report on innovative funding mechanism to support next-gen tangible ventures</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Five interviews with ecosystem experts; two founders and a collaborator and expert in open source manufacturing. • Workshop on Hybrid and Impact Funding <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many investors were introduced to the concept and value of makerspaces, resulting in heightened awareness and interest. • Innovative funding mechanisms tailored to the needs of makerspaces and startups were identified on the basis of research from sector practitioners and written sources. • Scalable recommendations for sustainable funding strategies for makerspaces in Europe and Africa were developed, ensuring long-term impact. • Deliverable 1.4: EU mAKE Innovative Financing Mechanisms – Funding Mechanisms for Makerspaces and Open Source Projects For Africa and Europe

1.5. Common Policy Agenda and Minister-meets-Makers events

Activities, outputs and outcomes related to the work with policy makers are summarised in the matrix below.

Table 10: Outputs and outcomes Common Policy Agenda

WP2 activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Collection, mapping and comparative analysis of case studies focused on how DIHs/makerspaces organise themselves in supportive structures for policy advocacy on national and regional levels</p>	<p>Outputs: D2.1: Report on National and Regional Hub Associations including 7 Documented Case Studies and Comparative Analyses (M12)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 5 case studies from Africa; 2 from Europe ● Recommendations for bottom-up approaches to multi-actor policy advocacy for DIHs/makerspaces <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Findings from Y1 case studies helped shape the themes and questions pursued in the Y2 FGDs and interviews (see below) ● Y1 case studies generated valuable contacts for setting up the Y2 FGDs and interviews
<p>Creation of a common policy agenda for makerspaces in Africa and Europe and recommendations for policy makers</p>	<p>Outputs: D2.2: Common Policy Agenda and Recommendations for Policy Makers (M24)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 11 FGDs (10 virtual and one in-person at an event) ● 7 interviews (virtual) ● A total of 69 participants in the FGDs/interviews: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 26 participants from Africa ● 43 participants from Europe ● 26 participants (makers, DIH/makerspace leaders, local government representative, experts) in 13-Dec-2023 mAKE webinar focused on development of common policy agenda ● Engagement with makerspaces on mAKE project at AfriLabs Annual Gathering, Kigali, Oct. 2023 ● Presentation of mAKE project at Ghana Digital Innovation Week (GDIW), Accra, Nov. 2023, with attendance by 35 GDIW delegates ● Awareness-raising on mAKE project during Africa Makerspace Network (AMN) Study Programme, May 2023, with mAKE session attended by 16 participants ● Deliverable D2.2 completed <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Stakeholder inputs during December 2023 mAKE webinar ensured that the WP remains cognizant of the need to collaborate with local decision-makers and local institutions in policy formulation ● Stakeholder inputs during December 2023 webinar prompted the WP to work towards development of a policy brief

<p>Dissemination, documentation and report of "Minister meet Maker" Dialogue events</p>	<p>D2.3 Dissemination documentation and report of "Minister meet Maker" Dialogue events (M34)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 11 Events for Dissemination of the policy (9 in person events and 2 virtual) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 6 events held in Africa <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Ghana Digital Innovation Week 2023, Ghana ■ Ghana Digital Innovation Week 2024, Ghana ■ Ghana Hubs Network General Meeting ■ Africa Open Science Hardware 2024, Ghana ■ Africa Makerspaces Ecosystem Gathering 2024 ■ Afrilabs Annual Gathering Makerspace Track, South Africa ○ 4 events held in Europe <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Vulca seminar 2024, Germany ■ Wind empowerment Conference and Workshop, Greece ■ Distributed Design Platform and mAKE Collaborative Policy Workshop, Spain ■ Vulca seminar 2023, Slovenia ○ 2 virtual events <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Transformation Literacy Conference ■ Community call ● Over 400 participation from stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 42 of the participants are policy makers, government officials and aid to governments ○ Over 100 participants are makers ○ Over 250 participants are in the private sector ● Over 360 request of the policy document in just October 2024 to Jan 2025 ● Over 850 social media reach <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ YouTube 343 views, and 18 likes ○ Instagram 126 likes of common policy materials ○ LinkedIn 384 likes on common policy matters <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enhanced awareness among stakeholders about the impact of makerspaces and Common Policy Agenda recommendations. ● Strengthened relationships between policymakers and makers through dialogue and shared experiences. ● Increased commitment from government officials to support the agenda, as evidenced by their participation in events. ● Broader public engagement via social media and virtual platforms, ensuring inclusivity in the dissemination process.
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1.6. Open Makerspace Toolkit and Training-of-trainers

Activities, outputs and outcomes related to the work with policy makers are summarised in the matrix below.

Table 11: Outputs and outcomes Makerspace Toolkit and ToTs

WP3 planned activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Develop an Open Makerspace Toolkit, comprising OERs on how to set up, manage, equip, and sustain different types of digital innovation makerspaces</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <p>D3.1: Open Makerspace Toolkit</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online survey to collect OERs: 15 high-quality responses received from external stakeholders • Collection and review of approximately 400 existing OERs with potential relevance to the Toolkit • Selection of elements of approximately 80 existing OERs for inclusion in the Toolkit, with emphasis on elements with strong relevance to the maker movement and/or social innovation • Inclusion, in the Toolkit, of elements of 3 OERs created by the mAKE project • Online publication of Open Makerspace Toolkit (M24), comprising OERs on how to set up, manage, equip, and sustain different types of digital innovation makerspaces: https://pressbooks.pub/omt4make • Open Makerspace Toolkit accessed online by 1312 visitors (Nov 2023 to Jan 2025); downloaded 185 times from the mAKE website (Oct 2024 to Jan 2025) <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The discovery of the rapid pace of development of new OERs relevant to DIHs/makerspaces made it necessary to host the Toolkit on a platform that allows for easy updating. Accordingly, the Pressbooks platform, https://pressbooks.com, was chosen • It was determined that the target number of OERs included in the Toolkit needed to be revised downwards from the originally projected target, so as to be able to focus more on quality than quantity
<p>Plan and organise training-of-trainers events</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <p>Planning and organising of the first training-of-trainers event, March 2024, in Barcelona (with 12 participants)</p> <p>Planning and organising of the second training-of-trainers event, April 2024, in Yaoundé (with 13 participants)</p> <p>Planning and organising the third training-of-trainers event, April 2024, in Abidjan (with 10 participants)</p> <p>Planning and organising the fourth training-of-trainers event, June 2024, in Berlin (with 10 participants)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning and organising the fourth training-of-trainers event, July 2024, in Ghana (with 29 participants) <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ToTs supported makerspace representatives to create new makerspaces or run their makerspaces more efficiently and sustainably • Strong interest by local makerspace members to participate in the ToTs

WP3 planned activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Integration of a training based on the Toolkit into existing events or offering of trainings on a monthly basis

1.7. Maker passports

Activities, outputs and outcomes related to the Maker Passport are summarised in the matrix below.

Table 12: Outputs and outcomes maker passports

Planned activities	Outputs and initial outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Developing mutual recognition of hardware DIH users' skills using Maker Passports (based on people and skills standard (PSS) metadata document)</p> <p>Implement a Maker Passport prototype system for proof of concept</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 4th release of the PSS schema ● Proposed changes on the PSS schema - https://g33k.holbrook.no/a2ef19b045fa37a0058e3ab19afa4214b5e7997ba4c35c37101a3a00967c7bf9 ● Case study for a flexible structure for certification with H-FabLab from the REFFAO https://community.internetofproduction.org/t/people-and-skills-certifications-case-study/683 ● Presentation of the PSS and the community-based authentication method for maker passport to community calls (REFFAO and AOSH) ● Maker Passport prototype systems (method 1 community-based authentication process to be continued and method 2 badging systems) ● Maker Passport platform https://maker-passport.fly.dev/profiles <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PSS provides a framework for creating a record of skills and training for a maker to showcase his expertise ● Choices of systems to turn learned skills into digital certifications that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Facilitates global collaboration and skill sharing ○ Facilitates search of makers, peers and mentors: identify and mobilize ○ Showcases skills and opens doors to new spaces and places

1.7. Map of Machinery

Activities, outputs and outcomes related to the Map of Machinery are summarised in the matrix below.

Table 13: Outputs and outcomes map of machinery

Planned activities	Output and initial outcomes at the end of Y3
<p>Mapping of machinery in and near DIHs/makerspaces across Africa and Europe</p> <p>Collection of data and wrangling to Open Know-Where standard</p> <p>Publishing of existing data</p> <p>Creation and testing of data upload processes</p> <p>Uploading of new data</p> <p>Cooperate with WP1 regarding the venture building opportunities</p> <p>Clarify with start-ups the usefulness of the mAKE map</p> <p>Cooperate with WP2 regarding the collective associations</p>	<p>Output:</p> <p>Map of Machinery developed with new design and new functionalities</p> <p>Data collection processes updated with the usage of KoboToolbox as a crucial tool for collecting device and location metadata, and enabling efficient data filtering.</p> <p>Data published:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open data set of makerspaces on the map of makerspaces: https://explore.openaire.eu/search/dataset?pid=10.5281%2Fzenodo.8383704 doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8383704, 10.5281/zenodo.8383705 Open data for the machines and tools in global makerspaces https://explore.openaire.eu/search/dataset?pid=10.5281%2Fzenodo.8383728 doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8383728, 10.5281/zenodo.8383729 A GIT repository containing Jupyter notebooks for the collection and analysis of machinery and facilities https://github.com/iop-alliance/okw_data_management/tree/main/notebooks/data_collectors A data completion script using Natural Language Processing was executed https://github.com/iop-alliance/data_reports/blob/main/notebooks/machines_in_fablabs_worl_tags.ipynb <p>An overall count of *20,000 records was aggregated, and after filtering out were obtained *10,308 unique records with a minimal set of attributes “name, (latitude, longitude, or address), (capability or machine), and (URL, e-mail or phone number)”.</p> <p>Cooperation with WP1 and the makers in residence during the MiR programme leading to exchange of new data on machinery and materials.</p> <p>1:1 conversations shared on the IOP Forum on the usage of the map and how to further improve it: https://community.internetofproduction.org/t/okw-working-group-action-plan-step-1-one-to-one-conversations/647</p> <p>Cooperation with WP2 for the presentation of the map and WP4 technical innovation at AOSH community call.</p> <p>mAKE Talk: https://youtu.be/MJYyIH-xMnE?si=XRa482O9vf4Qb38k</p> <p>Outcome:</p> <p>Finding manufacturing sites for open-source projects, and stimulating local economic growth with new business opportunities and job creation.</p>

	<p>In case of emergency, localising and accessing critical supplies for a quick response.</p> <p>Making local production more efficient and collaborative: “With the map of the machinery, we are able to know the machines found in different makerspaces– making it easy to work together on different projects and meet tight deadlines. Even share learnings from machine operations and project executions.”</p> <p>Raising awareness and confidence to locally produce when getting access to local data on spaces, machinery and materials.</p>
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1.8. Digital contracting system

Activities, outputs and outcomes related to the digital contracting system are summarised in the matrix below.

Table 14: Outputs and outcomes digital contracting system

WP4 activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Digital contracting system to distribute production across the DIHs/makerspaces network</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital contracting system prototype. https://distributed-orders.fly.dev/ • Workflow automation implemented available in repository: https://github.com/iop-alliance/distributed-contracts-trials • Building a distributed contracting system– Internet of Production Community Call (July 2024) https://youtu.be/r8aLvH4wTAY?si=IS4vhmSX3u8QbxYL • Contracting for distributed manufacturing was tested by 27 makers with a model contract in 2023. Since October 2024, approx. 62 people have tested the digital contracting system.. <p>Initial outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential for democratizing and boosting local production, reducing costs, lowering environmental impact, particularly in underserved regions. • Challenges were identified, like quality assurance, role clarity and legal considerations, as areas requiring further exploration for scalability.

1.9. mAKE Community Building

WP6 activities	Outputs and outcomes at end of Y3
<p>Manage the community</p> <p>Facilitate and support results sharing and embedding</p>	<p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deliverable D6.3: Co-Creation Report (M34) Deliverable D6.4: Sustaining mAKE (M36) 107.200 engagements from the mAKE community 148 online and 56 offline events 13 WP6 community calls and/or webinars produced 7 mAKE Talks 19 resources embedded Over 100 collaborative resources on the mAKE MOOC platform Collaboration with WP1 on launch of community programme MIR 3.0 105 participants in the mAkErspace Track at Afrilabs Annual Summit 2 ICT-58 interviews and 2 collaborative calls 1 mAKE legacy secretariat formed <p>Ongoing outcomes:</p> <p>Strong mutual learning and experience-sharing between WP6 and other WPs, e.g.,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With WP1, via collaboration on the continued OCBM, MiR 3.0 • With WP5, via collaboration on community discussion webinars, mAKE Talks, and communications related to key deliverables <p>Awareness of mAKE among the project’s stakeholder groups has continually grown through the project’s use of numerous activation and engagement methods</p> <p>Mutual learning and experience-sharing, between the mAKE consortium and the project’s stakeholders, has continued to be facilitated through the activation and engagement activities</p> <p>mAKE collaboration with the Vulca network, enabled by Vulca’s membership WP lead entity GIG, has greatly strengthened mAKE’s ability to deliver the MiR programme (i.e., MiR 3.0)</p>

Feedback from Participants:

Venture Building Program and Cairo Trip:

How satisfied are you with the overall support provided by the program?

8 Antworten

Figure 12: Satisfaction program support

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016858.

With how many investors have you approximately exchanged during this trip?

6 Antworten

Figure 13: No. of exchange with investors

Would you recommend other startups to join such a trip?

6 Antworten

Figure 14: Recommendations to other startups

Venture Building Handbook:

How would you rate the usefulness of the Venture Building Handbook in supporting your companies, makerspace or project development?

15 Antworten

Figure 15: Usefulness Venture Building Handbook

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016858.

What initial impacts have you experienced after reviewing the Venture Building Handbook?

15 Antworten

Figure 16: Initial impact Venture Building Handbook

Approximately how many startups outside of the mAKE cohort have you met during this trip?

6 Antworten

Figure 17: Meeting with other startups

Which topics have you been discussing?

6 Antworten

Figure 18: Topics of discussion

9th of May - Business 2 Business Matchmaking session (during and after pitch training session): Kindly specify the startups with whom you envision fostering future collaborations:

Figure 19: Future collaboration potentials

Figure 20: ToT Feedback to questionnaires

